

SOlutions TEsting for Regions through Insurance for Climate Adaptation

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2	I-Catalist SL	ICA	ES	Beneficiary
3	Climate Risk Advisory Ltd	CRA	NO	Beneficiary
4	Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research	UFZ	DE	Beneficiary
5	SINTEF AS	SINTEF	NO	Beneficiary
6	Mitigrate AS	MITI	NO	Beneficiary
7	AQUATEC	AQUA	ES	Beneficiary
8	Genillard & Co GmbH	G&Co	DE	Beneficiary
9	National Center for Scientific Research Demokritos	DEMO	GR	Beneficiary
10	Hochschule Weihenstephan-Triesdorf	HSWT	DE	Beneficiary
11	Association for the Development of West Athens	ASDA	GR	Beneficiary
12	Behavior SMART OOD	BES	BG	Beneficiary
13	Conselleria de Generalitat Valenciana	GVA	ES	Beneficiary
14	Municipality of Gabrovo	MoG	BG	Beneficiary
15	Empower Insight	EI	FR	Beneficiary
16	Stiftung Global Infrastructure Basel	GIB	CH	Associated Partner
17	Verbraucherzentrale Sachsen e.V.	VZS	DE	Associated Partner
18	Landesamt für Umweltschutz (Regional Env. Protection Agency)	LAU	DE	Associated Partner
19	KLP Skadeforsikring AS (insurance)	KLP	NO	Associated Partner
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23	German Insurance Association	GDV	DE	Associated Partner
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25	Bavarian Farmers Association	BBV	DE	Associated Partner
26	Zadar County, Croatia	ZDC	HR	Associated Partner
27	The County Governor in Trøndelag	CGT	NO	Associated Partner
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29	Caisse de Reassurance (insurance)	COR	FR	Associated Partner
30	Hellenic Association of Insurance Companies	HAIC	GR	Associated Partner

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Abbreviations

AS	Associated Partner
CA	Consortium Agreement
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
CL	Case Leader
CoP	Communities of Practises
CT	Coordination Team
DoA	Document of the Action
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
NBS	Nature-Based solutions
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
SRL	Societal Readiness Level
TL	Task Leader
TRL	Technical Readiness Level
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

This deliverable identifies systemic drivers and barriers to climate-related risk and loss data exchange, offering practical solutions to improve data quality and unlock market opportunities.

This report examines the drivers and barriers for recording, collecting, storing, and sharing climate-related risk and loss data across three European regions: Gabrovo (BG), Valencia (ES), and Trøndelag (NO). Using a matrix combining the dimensions of a PESTEL (Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental, and Legal) analysis¹ and the Capability, Opportunity, and Motivation (COM-B) framework², it identifies key governance, legal, technical, economic, and behavioural factors that enable or hinder data exchange. The report outlines how these barriers can be overcome to ensure data quality, and provides a basis for exploring opportunities for enabling the efficient utilisation of climate risk & loss data.

What this deliverable presents:

- Identifies tangible **drivers and barriers** for recording, collecting, storing, and sharing climate-risk and loss data (via **PESTEL**).
- Offers a behavioral analysis of the intangible and perception barriers that block efficient recording, collecting, storing and sharing of climate risk and loss data (employing the COM-B model).
- Applies a drivers-barriers analysis to the three case study regions using a PESTEL/COM-B matrix to analyse the factors that block and can enable effective recording, collecting, storing and sharing of climate risk and loss data.

The combined **PESTEL–COM-B analysis** reveals that the barriers to effective recording, collection, storage, and sharing of climate-related risk and loss data are both **structural and behavioural**. While the PESTEL framework exposes systemic gaps - fragmented mandates, unclear legal provisions, weak coordination, and uneven infrastructure, the COM-B model explains why these persist: capability deficits, limited opportunities for collaboration, and low motivation among key actors.

Across the three SOTERIA pilot regions - Gabrovo (BG), Valencia (ES), and Trøndelag (NO) - the analysis shows a gradient of maturity. Gabrovo illustrates an early-stage environment with minimal structures and awareness of the importance of

¹ Johnson, G., Scholes, K., & Whittington, R. (2008).

Exploring Corporate Strategy (8th ed.). Pearson Education.

² Michie, S., van Stralen, M. M., & West, R. (2011). *The behaviour change wheel: A new method for characterising and designing behaviour change interventions*. *Implementation Science*, 6(42). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1748-5908-6-42>

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climate-related risk and loss data management; Valencia combines strong legal foundations with weak incentives; and Trøndelag demonstrates advanced systems but ongoing behavioural and coordination challenges.

Common barriers include fragmented governance, lack of financial or reputational incentives, low trust, and inconsistent data use. Emerging drivers include clear legal mandates, visible cost–benefit value, peer networks that foster reciprocity, interoperable technology supported by training, and the use of environmental events as catalysts for cooperation.

Overall, the findings confirm that closing the climate-risk data gap requires aligning systemic readiness with behavioural enablers ensuring that the institutions, norms, and motivations behind data sharing evolve together.

1. Introduction

a. Purpose and Scope

The problem addressed in this report is the fragmented and inconsistent landscape for recording, collecting, storing, and sharing climate-related risk and loss data. Despite growing policy attention and technological capacity, data remains siloed, underused, lack of re-used, or inaccessible, often due to legal constraints, behavioural inertia, and infrastructural gaps. This fragmentation undermines the ability of both public and private actors to make informed, timely, and efficient decisions about climate adaptation, risk management, and insurance design.

To address this challenge, it is essential to understand the full range of barriers that hinder the necessary transition to new models, processes, and collaboration dynamics between the public and private entities that enable, facilitate, and rely on effective climate data exchange. Reliable and interoperable climate-related risk and loss data have become critical assets in today's climate realities: they underpin decisions that reduce vulnerability, lower costs, and support smarter adaptation measures. When such data flows are limited or poorly coordinated, opportunities to reduce losses and manage climate-related risks are limited.

This report therefore **aims to map both the barriers that obstruct and the drivers that can accelerate the transition to more effective models of data recording, collection, storage, and sharing.** By identifying these systemic enablers and obstacles, we can **outline realistic and context-grounded recommendations for how this transition can take place in practice.**

Our analytical approach distinguishes between *tangible (objective)* and *intangible (perceptual or behavioural)* factors. Tangible drivers and barriers are those rooted in governance structures, legal frameworks, infrastructure, technology, or economic incentives. They are analysed through a PESTEL framework, which captures the political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal dimensions influencing data exchange. However, transitions of this kind rarely depend on technical capacity alone. They also require changes in how institutions and individuals behave. Many actors tend to adhere to established routines and processes, even when objective barriers have been removed. This behavioural resistance is a natural feature of human decision-making and institutional culture. To capture it, the report complements the PESTEL analysis with the COM-B behavioural model, which helps identify motivation, opportunity, and capability-related factors that affect the willingness and ability of stakeholders to act in new ways to support effective recording, collecting, storing, and sharing climate-related risk and loss data.

By examining both tangible and intangible dimensions, we seek to understand not only *what* needs to change but also *how* that transition can realistically occur. This dual perspective enables us to recommend interventions that go beyond technical or regulatory fixes and address the behavioural and organizational dynamics that often determine success or failure.

Finally, the analytical frameworks are applied to three regional case studies within the SOTERIA project - Gabrovo (Bulgaria), Valencia (Spain), and Trøndelag (Norway). Each represents a distinct socio-economic and climatic context, providing a valuable testing ground for assessing how systemic barriers and drivers manifest in practice. This application allows us to verify the robustness and real-world relevance of our approach and to draw lessons that can inform broader European efforts to create an environment in which climate-related risk and loss data are effectively recorded, shared, and used to support smarter adaptation and more resilient insurance systems.

b. Why Now?

Climate-related losses are rising across Europe, creating growing urgency for improving how risk and loss data are recorded, connected, and used. The economic and social costs of extreme weather events continue to escalate, yet the ability to quantify and anticipate these risks remains constrained by fragmented data systems. At the same time, the policy landscape is shifting and EU initiatives increasingly encourage data reuse, interoperability, and open access as key enablers of resilience and innovation³.

These dynamics signal a critical moment to move toward a more coherent and holistic approach that encourages and supports recording, collecting, storing, and sharing climate-related risk and loss data across different European contexts. This would be key to enable the turning of isolated datasets into actionable intelligence allowing decision-makers, insurers, and local authorities to see a fuller picture of exposure, vulnerability, and loss.

Encouragingly, successful examples already exist and offer best practices along with relevant lessons learned. *Norway's Knowledge Bank*⁴ demonstrates that effective public-private data collaboration is both possible and highly beneficial. By connecting data across institutions and sectors, such models reveal how shared information can

³ European Environment Agency (EEA). (2025, 14 October). *Economic losses from weather- and climate-related extremes in Europe*. Retrieved from [EEA website]. [European Environment Agency](#)

⁴ OECD (2021), "Scaling Up Government-To-Government Knowledge Co-operation", in Development Co-operation Profiles: In Practice, OECD Publishing, Paris, [Case Study](#).

enhance risk understanding, support better insurance design, flourish new innovation, and accelerate adaptation to a changing climate.

c. Methodology

The methodology combines two complementary analytical lenses - PESTEL and COM-B - to capture both the structural and behavioural dimensions of data governance and exchange.

1. PESTEL analysis provides a macro-contextual mapping of systemic enablers and constraints in each region. It identifies the political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal factors that influence data-related practices. These include governance frameworks, funding mechanisms, societal attitudes, technological infrastructures, environmental pressures, and regulatory requirements that collectively determine the conditions under which data is generated, maintained, and shared.
2. The COM-B model adds a behavioural perspective, examining how these structural conditions translate into the actions, motivations, and decisions of key stakeholders. It focuses on three interrelated determinants:
 - **Capability** – the psychological and physical ability of individuals and institutions to engage in new data practices;
 - **Opportunity** – the external enablers or constraints, such as institutional support or market incentives, that make behavioural change possible; and
 - **Motivation** – the reflective and automatic drivers that shape willingness, priorities, and commitment to act differently.

Fig. 1: The COM-B Model: Enabling Behaviour Change⁵

By combining PESTEL dimensions with COM-B factors, the analysis links external systemic drivers with internal behavioural mechanisms. This combined approach clarifies not only which external conditions affect data management, but also how these conditions manifest in stakeholder behaviours, whether as barriers or enablers to effective data exchange. The result is a more complete understanding of both the visible and underlying forces that influence the transition toward smarter, more integrated, and adaptive climate risk data ecosystems.

Data sources for this deliverable include the SOTERIA Pilot Story Maps and complementary project reports (especially D1.3⁶), regional PESTEL matrices co-developed with pilot partners, and behavioural insights from the Knowledge Bank case in Norway (part 4 of this report). Evidence was synthesised across these sources to identify priority actions, stakeholder incentives, and strategic recommendations.

d. Definitions

In this deliverable, climate-related risk and loss data refers to structured information that supports the assessment and management of climate hazards and their impacts across sectors, and administrative levels. The term spans risk data (potential impacts)

⁵ Recreated by the authors based on (Michie, van Stralen, & West, 2011).

⁶ [D1.3. FINAL Recommendation for developing regional data hubs: Mechanisms, challenges, and best practices for climate-related risk and loss data integration - Google Dokumenter](#)

and loss data (realised impacts), with distinct attributes, access conditions, and privacy requirements.

The report adopts a comprehensive perspective on the entire data management process. All analyses, insights, and recommendations consider the full sequence of activities involved in recording, collecting, storing, and sharing climate-related risk and loss data as an integrated system. References in the text to “data management,” “data processes,” or “data exchange” should therefore be understood to include all these interconnected stages, unless explicitly specified otherwise. This approach ensures that the findings and recommendations address the systemic nature of data flows and the interdependencies between different steps in the process.

2. PESTEL Analysis of Factors Shaping Climate-Risk & Loss Data

1.1 Political drivers and barriers

2.1.1 Overview

The political analysis in a PESTEL normally identifies threats and weaknesses related to government policies, leadership, and change needed due to climate change and sustainability issues. Climate politics would be influenced by a number of social and political movements focused on different parts of building political will for climate action. It could be the climate justice movement, youth climate movement and threat of litigation. However, politicians are “**bound**” by their political programs and popularities by voters, which normally builds on **short-term strategies**, and will influence the willingness or unwillingness to use tax policy, regulation or de-regulation for climate transition to zero fossil fuel and, lastly, prioritizing resources and funding/financing for climate adaptation actions in national and local budgets. Also, adapting to climate change and managing climate risk are costly endeavors, especially for local governments with **limited capacity**. In many jurisdictions, fiscal challenges are already putting infrastructure and services under increasing stress⁷.

2.1.2 Awareness

Often regulations require the local government to **assess the consequences** of climate change, and in their forward-looking risk assessment use the highest climate projection as a basis. Normally national authorities provide guidelines and offer county-specific climate profiles as an important part of the knowledge base. The local planning authority must itself assess the need to supplement national and regional information with knowledge of local conditions, including **previous undesirable natural events**.

Yet, do they have the right data to be able to do this process? Governments face a choice when determining investments, commonly using cost-benefit analysis to guide decisions. Such analysis estimates the advantages and disadvantages of different options usually in monetary terms. This helps determine which path provides the most

⁷ <https://carnegieendowment.org/research/2025/08/managing-climate-risk-implications-for-local-governments?lang=en>

benefits net of costs.⁸ When making these analyses in political and operational decisions, **governments need concrete and reliable data**, making them aware of the challenges and needs related to climate change, what type of measures to choose and where to implement climate adaptation measures.

Publicly available national and local statistics show that the key data sources for climate-related loss and damage data are based on **insurance data, offering the most precise view of damage**, trends and patterns to insured assets. Very little impact data from disaster/events and historical loss data originate from national or local governments, thus, depending on the maturity of the country in collecting, systemizing and sharing these data.

The non-life insurance data would normally show the cause of the damage (sewer backup, surface/storm water, riverine flooding, type of landslide etc.), the day the damage occurred, what was damaged, and the location/address of the insurance object that was damaged. It further shows the compensation/pay-out to the policyholder, which will reflect the insurance agreement/contract. The data are typically digitised, and when compiled to a larger area it will provide **which areas being most exposed**, and from what type of hazard, showing both individual and total insured costs. The areas will therefore show which areas are exposed to repeated damage, unless preventive measures are implemented. The data are also a good basis for **vulnerability analysis** in combination with other data sources like gender, income and other demographic and geographic data. This climate data can also be combined with other open sources from satellite, modelling, and observational systems (e.g., Copernicus, CORDEX), including crowdsourced/citizen science data, OpenStreetMap and app-based disaster reporting.

In European countries with **low insurance penetration**, standardized and compiled climate-related risk and loss data from national (public) compensation schemes is often poor or lacking, leading to less awareness among politicians and other decision-makers and a fault in the basis for optimal decisions.

The insurance industry has taken a more active role in advocating politicians and the society by using their insurance statistics and extensive experience from handling claims. They raise awareness of the increased costs due to climate-related natural catastrophes, and the need for updated codes/rules and more public spending on preventive measures. For example, Insurance Europe, the European insurance association, representing the insurance and reinsurance sector, lobbies before EU bodies, public affairs, industry forums, contributing to climate risk information within the political, social, business and economic environment. The data are pivotal in the

⁸ [Managing Climate Risks, Facing up to Losses and Damages \(EN\)](#)

discussion on climate adaptation and in contributing to awareness in their dialogue with politicians and other decision-makers.

The **insurance companies play an important role in the resilience transition** through insurance risk pricing and contract conditions, either setting conditions to companies providing service in their value chain, or conditions set in the insurance contract with their policy holders. With these “tools” they can influence individuals and entities behaviour towards more climate-resilient practices, e.g. by premium discounts for property owners who implement flood mitigation measures, and higher premiums for buildings in high-risk areas are an incentive not to build in such areas⁹. This knowledge and resources can help reduce vulnerabilities, support fair transitions and strengthen the resilience of societies in the face of an increasingly unstable climate. Thus, insurance models, used to calculate the price of the insurance policy, need to be able to consider the risk reduction potential of measures so that the insurance premium can be determined accordingly.

On the other hand, a barrier is that the main incentive for policyholders in choosing an insurer, or moving to another insurer, is normally the insurance premium. Not the condition under the insurance contract, as they are often complex and not easy to fully comprehend. This means that if a company sets conditions which would incentivize the policyholder to be more resilient, but with a slightly higher premium, the policyholders would choose the insurance company offering the insurance cover without these incentives.

2.1.3 Motivation

The **burden of responding to extreme weather** will fall mostly on local governments/municipalities, which are responsible for the majority of a country’s infrastructure spending, as well as basic welfare benefits such as schooling, kindergarten, social assistance, child welfare, medical care and nursing homes. In addition, the municipality must administer laws and regulations, be an active social developer, and ensure a vibrant local democracy.

Climate adaptation is a **cross-sectoral consideration** that requires coordination and cooperation across sectors, and between municipal, county and state bodies. Work on climate adaptation should contribute to society becoming better equipped to meet climate change, by ensuring that municipalities and county authorities avoid or limit risks, vulnerabilities and disadvantages, and benefit from any opportunities resulting from changes in the climate.

To be able to fulfill this role and obligations, access to climate-related risk and loss data is essential, and an enabler for climate adaptation knowledge and action.

⁹ [Insurance Matters - Climate change & sustainability](#)

Findings from SOTERIA, based on dialogue with the pilot regions, show they **need granular data** for the data to be useful in adaptation work. Aggregated data can give awareness and motivation to act, but they are not sufficient when it comes to operational and concrete actions and measures.

The dialogue with the pilot regions further shows the data are a profound **necessity to make risk assessments**, and better understanding of (rising) costs and risk related to climate change. An example from the Oslo city/municipality showed that the city's administration successfully used ten years of climate-related insurance data (received from the insurance companies via their association), to make the city's politicians increase finance for climate adaptation in the budget. On the other hand, the availability and use of insurance data for adaptation implicates political willingness to prioritize resources and financing, the development of **new competences and expertise**, and new routines to be able to fully take advantage of the data in climate adaptation.

2.1.4 Barriers

Findings from dialogues with, and questionnaires to, the regional pilots show a variety of barriers related to climate-related risk and loss data, which we believe are replicable to many regions across Europe. One major barrier present in all the cases is that **fragmented data is dispersed** among insurers, municipalities, national agencies, public funds, and scientific projects. This makes it difficult for decision makers to have the correct risk picture, prioritize in their budgets and take the right decisions. Another barrier is the lack of common standards, either within the insurance sector or within the public sector, where each actor classifies and records differently. Each actor or institution, e.g. land-use planning and infrastructure/water & sewage, needs detailed and granular data. A barrier at the local level, especially in smaller municipalities, is the capacity gap: they often lack experts and technical resources to be able to use and analyse the data.

Climate models that incorporate future climate change projection data with (historical) physical data and climate-related data from various sources would give the comprehensive and holistic risk picture, and could be an important driver for action both on the political level and in businesses.

Barriers for regions and municipalities are the **lack of knowledge and understanding of the need** to prioritize purchasing, often expensive, models. Knowledge on which model would be the most beneficial and being able to use, analyze and implement the data into existing platforms and systems, often requires new skills and experts.

2.2 Economic barriers and drivers

2.2.1 Overview

Economic factors play a central role in enabling or constraining the sharing and integration of climate-related risk and loss data. **Costs associated with standardisation, infrastructure development, and governance** must be weighed against long-term benefits such as improved risk management, more effective adaptation investments, and alignment with EU sustainability frameworks. Market dynamics, regulations, and financial incentives shape whether insurers, public authorities, and municipalities engage in data-sharing. While compliance with legal and governance requirements can raise costs, carefully designed financial mechanisms, regulatory instruments, and public–private partnerships (PPPs) can transform these challenges into **opportunities** and support the creation of sustainable, scalable data ecosystems.

2.2.2 Drivers

Access to granular insurance and loss data supports more accurate risk assessments, which in turn enable better pricing of insurance products and the design of targeted adaptation measures. Such data also provides concrete evidence of the **financial impacts of natural hazards**. This enhances cost–benefit analyses and allows decision-makers to allocate resources more efficiently by prioritizing the most vulnerable areas, thereby improving the economic return on climate-related investments.

Whether sourced from insurers in high-coverage regions or from public institutions in areas with lower insurance penetration, loss data is essential for understanding the evolving impacts of climate change. It can also play a key role in informing political budget processes and guiding public investment strategies. Regardless of the provider, the economic value of data increases when it is comparable across sources. Voluntary alignment can therefore be an important driver: insurers, for example, may adopt common taxonomies or definitions for loss data through industry associations or collaborative platforms when such efforts are backed by resources or deliver better sector-wide insights.

Pooling resources through PPP and shared data hubs can generate economies of scale and reduce the financial burden for individual stakeholders. Regulatory initiatives, such as the EU Taxonomy, may reinforce these dynamics by classifying data-sharing activities as sustainable economic practices and linking them to access to green finance or enhanced market positioning. In addition, systematic data sharing has the potential to increase transparency in public spending, which could strengthen accountability and support more efficient allocation of resources over the long term.

To unlock this value, municipalities and public agencies need tools that can translate data into insights. Shared approaches to data collection and analysis can help in reducing duplication, lowering transaction costs, and make planning and procurement processes more efficient. Standardized frameworks also strengthen the purchasing power of municipalities and public agencies by allowing them to compare solutions and avoid dependence on a single proprietary software provider. This can improve long-term cost efficiency and stimulate competition, as service providers are able to develop new analytic tools on top of open standards. Greater interoperability also enables the adoption of free and open-source software, lowering barriers for smaller municipalities and reducing reliance on proprietary systems.

A central part of SOTERIA is innovative insurance solutions to meet the insurance gap. We explore how **parametric insurance** can be an alternative to traditional insurance, especially in the agriculture sector, where the insurance penetration in Europe is very low. The insurance uses pre-defined triggers and measurable indexes, often from satellite data, which would bring more transparency, expedite claims processes and payouts, and reduce administrative and frictional costs.¹⁰ Sharing climate-related risk and loss data from parametric insurance could (also) be useful for end-users in the agriculture sector, and for public decision-makers in planning and understanding the **economic impact**. Parametric insurance could fill the protection gaps and protect vulnerable communities and economies from climate risks.

2.2.3 Barriers

Despite these drivers, several economic obstacles continue to **limit the integration of climate-risk and loss data**. Developing interoperable systems, harmonising data structures, and maintaining secure platforms requires significant upfront investment, which is unevenly distributed across stakeholders.

Standardizing, collecting and making data available is not only a matter of initial investment but also of recurring costs, since continuous updates, data management, and quality assurance need to be sustained over time. In the insurance sector, preparing and sharing loss data involves substantial effort and is unlikely to be sustained without new funding models or legal obligations. **Commercial sensitivities** can add to the challenge, as claims and loss data are often regarded as proprietary, and companies may fear competitive disadvantages if they share them. This reluctance often persists even where aggregated or anonymized data could generate significant public value.

Fragmentation also increases costs when stakeholders operate with incompatible systems or reporting practices, potentially creating duplicated efforts and complex data reconciliation processes. These challenges are most visible when data is shared at

¹⁰ [How parametric insurance is building climate resilience | World Economic Forum](#)

asset level, where variations in coding, categorisation, and metadata across providers complicate integration, but this is also where the greatest opportunity lies, as granular data can be aligned and linked with other datasets to unlock richer insights. If aggregation is applied, whether for privacy, reporting, or technical reasons, it can further undermine data quality by concealing critical details. Without clear fiscal incentives or cost-sharing mechanisms, stakeholders often hesitate to invest in harmonisation or to absorb the added workload of producing high-quality, standardised datasets.

Finally, the uneven availability of data across regions presents a structural barrier. In areas with low insurance penetration, insurer data provides only a partial picture of climate-related losses. Incorporating information from public compensation schemes, emergency funds, or other non-insurance sources can be both costly and complex, but may be necessary for a more complete understanding of climate-related losses.

2.3 Sociocultural (Behavioural) barriers and drivers

2.3.1 Overview

Sociocultural factors are **often underestimated as important barriers or drivers** in the development of efficient systems for recording, collecting, storing, and sharing climate-related risk and loss data. Yet, they frequently determine whether well-designed institutional frameworks and technological solutions can work in practice.

Relevant sociocultural factors in this context include **social norms, perceptions of ownership of data, trust relations** between the different stakeholders in the data management ecosystem, and the existence of mechanisms that facilitate trust and collaboration, such as communities of practice. All of these factors essentially **shape how individuals and institutions behave** within the data ecosystem. Understanding these factors is therefore essential for identifying the enabling conditions under which public and private entities can collaborate effectively and contribute to a shared data environment that benefits all stakeholders.

This section explores the key **barriers** that hinder such cooperation and the **drivers** that can enable a shift toward an open, trust-based, and mutually beneficial environment for data sharing.

2.3.2 Drivers

Building and institutionalising trust is one of the fundamental drivers of data sharing. Trust can be built and institutionalised through transparent governance, reciprocity, and clear rules of engagement. Mechanisms such as formal data-sharing agreements, neutral coordination platforms, and cross-sector steering groups can

create confidence that shared data will be used responsibly. Over time, consistent and transparent collaboration helps transform trust from a fragile interpersonal relationship into an embedded organisational norm.

Shifting organisational norms requires leadership and visible proof of value. When respected actors within a sector demonstrate that data collaboration leads to measurable improvements such as smarter risk reduction and prevention, better loss assessment, faster disaster recovery, or innovative insurance products, others are more likely to emulate these practices. Recognition schemes, peer-to-peer learning, and communication campaigns that showcase positive examples can serve as **social proof** that openness pays off. Gradually, a new norm of cooperation and transparency can replace the culture of control and caution.

A key sociocultural driver is the reframing of data from private property to **shared resource**. Climate-related risk and loss data inherently reflect collective realities that affect communities, regions, and entire sectors simultaneously. Promoting the concept of *data stewardship*, where institutions act as custodians of data for the public benefit can align behavioral patterns with collaboration rather than control. This shift requires consistent messaging, incentives aligned with data reuse and interoperability, and institutional support for open-data principles.

Clear **articulation and demonstration of benefits** are also crucial to sustaining engagement and commitment to data openness. Stakeholders are more motivated to share data when they can see the concrete returns, such as improved forecasting, access to new insurance products, or reduced recovery costs. Pilot projects and joint use cases that document these impacts make the benefits very tangible and obvious. When actors understand the collective gains and their own institutional advantages, willingness to collaborate increases significantly.

The formation of **Communities of Practice (CoPs)** is one of the most powerful drivers for embedding collaborative data cultures. These networks of professionals spanning public agencies, research institutions, insurers, and local governments, create informal but trusted spaces for dialogue, learning, and experimentation. CoPs help align language, expectations, and problem-solving approaches across sectors. By facilitating peer-to-peer support and shared ownership of outcomes, they make collaboration the default rather than the exception. Over time, active communities become self-sustaining ecosystems that reinforce trust and transparency.

Ultimately, successful collaboration depends on a **shared sense of purpose**. When stakeholders recognise that their efforts serve a common mission, including protecting resident communities, managing risk, and ensuring equitable adaptation, they are more likely to overcome institutional boundaries and act collectively. Participatory governance structures that allow diverse actors to co-define objectives and success metrics strengthen this sense of joint responsibility. Clear communication of shared

stakes and inclusive decision-making enable data exchange and frame it as a collective commitment to resilience and adaptation.

2.3.3 Barriers

Trust deficit is one of the most common barriers when it comes to data sharing. A **persistent lack of trust among institutions and sectors** remains a strong sociocultural barrier to approaching data with openness and readiness for collaboration. Many public authorities **fear that data may be misinterpreted or politicised**, while private entities **worry about losing competitive advantage** or revealing sensitive information. Historical experiences of data misuse or lack of reciprocity have amplified scepticism toward open collaboration. These trust deficits lead to siloed systems, duplication of effort, and missed opportunities for joint learning and coordinated action. Even when legal frameworks and technologies are in place, the absence of interpersonal and inter-institutional trust often prevents effective data exchange.

Restrictive social norms and institutional culture within organisations frequently reinforce conservative attitudes toward sharing data and information. Public institutions may **prioritise caution and control** over openness, perceiving data dissemination as a risk rather than a contribution. In private organisations, **proprietary attitudes toward data often dominate**, where information is treated as a strategic asset rather than a shared resource. These entrenched norms sustain the status quo bias - the tendency to maintain existing practices even when better alternatives exist. Without visible examples of safe and successful sharing, institutions rarely take the first step toward openness.

A related barrier is the widespread **perception of “data as ownership.”** Institutions that invest in collecting and maintaining data often regard themselves as its **proprietors, entitled to control access and use**. This perception is reinforced by administrative and financial systems that reward exclusivity and volume rather than collaboration and interoperability. The result is a fragmented ecosystem where valuable climate data are treated as institutional property, limiting their potential to generate shared benefits.

Even when trust exists, the motivation to participate in data-sharing initiatives may be weak if **the perceived benefits are unclear or uneven**. For many stakeholders, especially smaller local authorities, SMEs, or research organisations, the link between data sharing and tangible outcomes such as improved risk models, better insurance access, or cost savings remains abstract. This **lack of clear incentives** perpetuates disengagement and prevents actors from seeing themselves as part of a mutually beneficial data ecosystem.

Sociocultural factors form the invisible architecture upon which data collaboration stands. Trust, social norms, perceptions of ownership, perceived benefits, and shared purpose are not peripheral concerns but central determinants of whether the transition toward integrated climate risk data systems can succeed. Policies and technologies can only deliver their intended outcomes if they are embedded within social contexts that value openness, reciprocity, and collective benefit. By recognising and actively addressing these sociocultural dynamics through trust-building, incentive alignment, and community-based collaboration, countries across Europe can cultivate the social and human foundations necessary for a resilient and adaptive climate data ecosystem.

2.4 Technological barriers and drivers

2.4.1 Overview

Technology underpins the ability to collect, harmonize, and share climate-risk and loss data. It sets the conditions for how data can be accessed, processed, and utilized, which directly influences adoption and scalability. While robust technological frameworks have the potential to enable high-quality analysis and decision-making, fragmented infrastructures, inconsistent standards, and uneven adoption limit progress.

2.4.1 Drivers

The growing use of shared standards and frameworks is one of the strongest enablers of data exchange. Principles such as FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) have become an important benchmark for transparency and interoperability, while standardised metadata profiles such as STAC¹¹ or GeDCAT-AP¹², and **common ontologies reduce ambiguity and allow heterogeneous datasets to be aligned**. At the European level, infrastructures like Copernicus and the EU Risk Data Hub¹³ illustrate how interoperable tools can be embedded into local and national systems. Remote sensing, advanced modelling, and near real-time hazard monitoring are increasingly combined to inform not only early warning and emergency response, but also as inputs to risk and resilience assessments, where they can help anticipate vulnerabilities and inform pre-emptive adaptation measures.

Advances in data preparation and usability also serve as important drivers. Improved metadata allows users to discover data or evaluate coverage, accuracy, and

¹¹ DCAT-AP geospatial extension to the DCAT application profile for European data portals. Available at: https://knowledge-base.inspire.ec.europa.eu/evolution/good-practice-library/geodcat-ap_en

¹² SpatioTemporal Asset Catalogs (STAC). Available at: <https://stacspec.org/en/>

¹³ [DRMKC Risk Data Hub](#)

limitations, helping them judge fitness for purpose. The **concepts of Analysis-Ready Datasets (ARD) and Decision-Ready Indicators (DRI)** aims to shorten the path from raw inputs to actionable insights, making data more accessible to planners and policymakers. Emerging Geospatial Knowledge Infrastructures (GKIs) build on these advances by embedding ARD and DRI into spatial knowledge graphs, allowing dynamic, machine-interpretable linkages across hazards, assets, exposure, and vulnerability¹⁴. This “knowledge layer” intends to bridge the gap between data readiness and decision intelligence.

The SOTERIA ontology provides a concrete example of how these principles can be applied in practice¹⁵. Built on a graph database and accessed through an API, it links heterogeneous loss data with the European Risk Data Hub. By structuring relationships between loss events, hazard types, spatial locations, and aggregated metrics, it creates a semantic layer that translates fragmented inputs into the semantic models expected by the RDH. At the same time, the effectiveness of such systems depends on the quality and completeness of the underlying datasets, underscoring that innovation must go hand in hand with investment in data coverage and accuracy.

Technology is also critical in developing methods that balance accessibility with confidentiality. Aggregation and anonymisation workflows make it possible to use sensitive information, such as loss records while safeguarding privacy and competition interests. Federated data access models offer another approach where analysts log into secure environments to perform queries or run models without extracting the underlying data. Such solutions may reduce the administrative burden of data-sharing agreements, ensure that sensitive material remains under the control of the data holder, and allow for secure handling and deletion after use. In parallel, cloud-native formats and modern web APIs (such as the OGC API family¹⁶) make it possible to discover, access, and analyse large datasets directly in the cloud¹⁷. By lowering dependence on costly local infrastructure and enabling near real-time collaboration, these innovations provide multiple pathways to reconcile data protection with accessibility and strengthen the robustness of climate-risk data ecosystems.

2.4.3 Barriers

Climate-risk data is often fragmented across platforms, formats, and institutional silos, which can create obstacles for integration. These challenges may be compounded

¹⁴ See FGDC (2024). *Moving Beyond SDI to GKI to Bring Geospatial Awareness to LLMs to Support Climate and Disaster Resilience*. Available at: https://www.fgdc.gov/initiatives/disaster-risk-resilience/24-073_SDI_LLM_for_Resilience/view

¹⁵ SOTERIA API: Retrieving Aggregated Loss Data for RDH Integration. SINTEF. Available at: <https://gitlab.sintef.no/soteria-public/soteria-api-retrieving-aggregated-loss-data-for-rdh-integration/>

¹⁶ OGC API Standards. Open Geospatial Consortium. Available at: <https://ogcapi.ogc.org/>

¹⁷ *Cloud Native Geospatial Foundation Guide*. Available at: <https://guide.cloudnativegeo.org/>

when datasets are **built on inconsistent standards or when metadata is incomplete**. In many cases, the precision or completeness of available data does not fully meet the needs of local-scale assessments, and gaps in metadata can further reduce usability.

Bringing together information from insurance, infrastructure, environmental, and social domains tends to require complex efforts, and progress is slowed when ontologies or validation tools are not widely applied. Even where technical solutions are available, their uptake often appears uneven as larger organisations are often better placed to adopt advanced systems, while smaller municipalities or regional agencies may struggle with limited expertise or infrastructure. Such disparities can contribute to uneven analytical capacity, where some areas benefit from well-developed resources while others find it more difficult to participate fully in data-driven approaches. Broader assessments, such as the European Commission's *Open Data Maturity Index*, confirm significant differences in member states' readiness for open and interoperable data ecosystems¹⁸.

2.5 Environmental barriers and drivers

2.5.1 Overview

Rising temperatures, shifting precipitation patterns, and the increasing frequency and severity of extreme events highlight the urgency of building robust information systems. Floods, droughts, heatwaves, storms, and wildfires not only generate escalating economic and societal costs, they also reveal where existing data systems fall short. In this way, environmental pressures both create demand for more granular information and test the adequacy of current approaches. While historical loss data remains indispensable for calibrating models and establishing baselines, climate change is altering hazard probabilities and exposure patterns in ways that past records cannot fully capture. This makes it essential to combine empirical evidence with forward-looking projections if risk information is to remain relevant under changing conditions.

2.5.2 Drivers

A key driver is the **growing emphasis on risk transparency** in climate adaptation policy. European and national strategies increasingly require systematic risk assessments as a safeguard against “climate-blind” decisions. This reinforces

¹⁸ European Commission (2024). *Open Data Maturity Report 2024*. Available at: <https://data.europa.eu/en/open-data-maturity/2024>

incentives to gather, harmonize, and share loss data that can inform adaptation planning and disaster risk reduction.

The integration of climate projections with historical records is also an important enabler, allowing forward-looking models to account for both observed impacts and future scenarios. Such integration supports cost-benefit analyses of adaptation measures and strengthens the evidence base for prioritizing investments in resilience.

2.5.3 Barriers

At the same time, several barriers persist. In many regions, the prevailing **culture of adaptation** remains reactive rather than preventive, with more attention given to recovery after disasters than to long-term risk reduction. This limits incentives for systematic data collection or maintenance of comprehensive loss databases. In addition, while hazard maps and projections are increasingly available, detailed historical **loss data at the asset or household level is often lacking**. This constrains the calibration of risk models and reduces confidence in projected impacts. Environmental datasets themselves are frequently fragmented across institutions and platforms, complicating efforts to combine hazard, exposure, and vulnerability information into coherent risk frameworks.

2.6 Legal drivers and barriers²

2.6.1 Overview - EU regulation setting the scene

There are extensive EU frameworks related to weather and climate data and disaster risk data. This report will mention some of the most relevant regulations, as other tasks and deliverables under SOTERIA (e.g. T4.3. and D1.3) and have made extensive research and overview of framework and regulation on the EU level related to this type of data.

We find that the most relevant EU regulatory “drivers” for recording, collecting, storing and/or sharing environmental and climate-related risk and loss data are: the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR); the GreenData4All initiative; the Flood Directive; the INSPIRE Directive; the Directive on Access to Environmental Information; the Open Data Directive; the European Climate Law; the Solvency II (incl. national regulation on financial institution duty on confidentiality regarding customer relations); the EU Taxonomy and the EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change.

The *GDPR* is the data protection legislation within the European Union (in force since May 2018). It establishes a common framework to ensure the security and privacy of personal data throughout the European Economic Area (EEA). Its primary objective is to strengthen the fundamental rights of citizens in the digital era by ensuring that the

processing of personal data is lawful, transparent and strictly limited to what is necessary.

The *GreenData4All initiative* aims to help deliver on Europe's green and digital transformation by updating EU rules on environmental geospatial data and on public access to environmental information. The aim is to enable greater sharing of data between the public and private sectors and with the general public and unlock the full benefits of data sharing for data-driven innovation and evidence-based decisions.

The *Floods Directive* (Directive 2007/60/EC on the assessment and management of flood risks), require all EU countries to; (i) assess all areas where significant floods could take place, (ii) map the flood extent and assets and humans at risk in these areas, and (iii) take adequate and coordinated measures to reduce this flood risk. Both the European *Water Frame Directive* (Directive 2000/60/EC), the main law for water protection in Europe, and the Flood Directive provide frameworks to which regions can nest and prioritise work plans, reflective of their operational and natural environments.

The *Solvency II directive* (2009/138/EC) regulates the finance and insurance sector and sets conditions for how the insurance sector can collect, store, use, and share the data collected from their policyholders, depending on the type of insurance company (life insurance, non-life insurance, re-insurance etc.).

However, in insurance regulation at the EU level, there is no definition of a necessary level of mutualisation. While Solvency II ensures prudentially sound reserving against risks, it does not prescribe how far risks need to be shared. On the other hand, while product oversight and governance requirements require pricing and product design that is fair for a defined target market, this does not set the size of that market.¹⁹ EIOPA will also regularly re-assess the appropriateness of the requirements of the standard formula regarding natural catastrophe risk, and if necessary, provide suggestions for potential changes in Solvency II²⁰.

The *European Climate Law*, (EU 2021/1119), sets the legislative foundation for achieving climate neutrality across the European Union, with a main goal is to anchor the EU's commitment to climate neutrality by 2050 and as the basis for structured climate adaptation action.

The *EU taxonomy Regulation* (EU) 2020/852, is a classification system that defines which economic activities can be considered environmentally sustainable. This framework is a cornerstone of the EU's Sustainable Finance Action Plan, and its purpose is to channel private and public finance toward climate and environmental objectives, reduce greenwashing, and provide clarity to investors, companies, and regulators.

¹⁹ [Data as a driver of inclusion in insurance - EIOPA](#)

²⁰ [The role of insurers in tackling climate change: challenges and opportunities - EIOPA](#)

The EU Copernicus Climate Change Service²¹ (C3S) is not a regulation, but a tool which supports the ability to fulfill the regulation and provide authoritative information about the past, present and future climate in Europe to the society. Combined with the EU Risk Data Hub (RDH)²², a GIS web-based collaborative platform used to look up, host, and share disaster risk and loss data. These tools provide crucial information for early warning, disaster risk prevention, risk management, and climate adaptation. The data are shown on an aggregate (municipality) level as it needs to be aligned with the GDPR regulation.

2.6.2 Drivers

As data-driven decisions continue to steadily gain traction due to climate change, we are faced with many new questions: What data do we need to fulfill our commitments or legal obligations? **Who needs what type of data and on what level?** How to get access to the relevant data? How to know who has the relevant data and what data amongst all the extensive data do we need? How exactly can this data inform our decision making? Should decisions be data informed, or data supplemented?

The European Union provides **open data** available for any audience, or data that are limited and accessible for specific groups, e.g. for national authorities. An important tool for disaster risk data is the RDH with the Joint Research Centre (JRC). RDH is a Geographic Information System (GIS) web platform for the documentation, evaluation and sharing of disaster risk, damage, and loss data on a European scale. However, there is uncertainty on how often, and who uses the data. This could be due to several reasons, where one barrier mentioned by JRC is language and unawareness of the platform. It is not mandatory for the member states to upload national data in the risk hub.

For national authorities to collect, store and share climate-related risk and loss data normally follows commitments to follow up on supranational guidelines and legal framework. National goals to provide important and authoritative information to the society can in itself be a driver.

The **availability of data** at national and regional/local level varies within the European countries. When incorporating EU directives into national legislation member states have the freedom to choose the manner they see fit to fulfil the required objectives of the directive. The national laws and regulations will define the role and responsibility of public institutions normally on all levels (ministry, national agency, regional and local government), which are the main *source of* what data is needed to be able to fulfill these legal obligations. However, in what format and level national authorities make available data for region and local governments in this context, seems to vary from

²¹ [Copernicus](#)

²² [DRMKC Risk Data Hub](#)

country to country. Findings from SOTERIA show local authorities with the responsibility for implementing CCA strategies and measures, hereby setting conditions for private builders, wants standardized building codes, and access to granular data supporting their decision. As this makes their day-to-day work and legal fulfillment easier.

In EU environmental law, the **polluter pays principle**²³ is enacted to make the party responsible for producing pollution responsible for paying for the damage done to the natural environment. The rise in climate-related damage and economic losses has sharpened the question on who should be liable for paying the damages as a consequence of lack of prevention measures, e.g. could the damage be hindered if the municipality had prioritized maintenance and investment in infrastructure capacity to cope with more heavy precipitation? Why weren't the inhabitants warned about the extreme precipitation that caused the flooding?

The International Court of Justice issued a landmark advisory opinion in July 2025 declaring that all countries have a legal obligation to protect and prevent harm to the climate.²⁴ It is widely acknowledged that it is neither equitable nor viable for a society to impose the financial burden on the individual who has sustained harm due to another's culpable actions. Legal traditions across time and space have consistently attributed this responsibility to the perpetrator of the harmful act.

A municipality or a business developer being held **liable for the damage costs**, either directly or through subrogation, is a **strong driver for investing in preventive measures**. Municipalities have a legal duty to prevent their inhabitants from perils. It is well known that municipalities often allow business development in flood zones, often driven by a strained economy, need for income from new businesses or people moving to the region. Access to loss and damage data gives them risk awareness and risk assessment and better basis for investing in adaptation and preventive measures, or not allowing them to develop in the area. Especially in larger cities, often with a backlog on the water and sewage network due to **unwillingness to increase unpopular fees or taxes**.

Insurance companies will compensate loss to customers affected from natural perils, but the question is when should the polluter pay principle pay make the municipalities liable for damage cost? This could be e.g. where the municipality has not used the most updated available data, neglected upgrading the infrastructure, or not taken any actions to prevent damage from foreseen perils. In these causes the insurance companies should have the right to subrogate, placing the liability and costs with the municipality.

²³ [Ensuring that polluters pay - Environment - European Commission](#)

²⁴ [The World Court just ruled countries can be held liable for climate change damage – what does that mean for the US?](#)

Rise in insurance premium for householders due to increasing climate-related loss and damages is happening all over Europe, with possibilities of houseowner not getting renewed their insurance contract. A clear regulation based on the polluter pay principle is a strong driver. Sharing granular climate related risk and loss data with municipalities can hinder or reduce litigations and conflicts between after natural disasters.

2.6.3 Barriers

As environmental sustainability becomes increasingly central to policy agendas, legislation has evolved to guarantee the availability and accessibility of environmental information. These legal developments are key to promoting data reuse and interoperability between public and private actors.

Environmental authorities usually have overall responsibility for climate change adaptation, whereas authorities for disaster management, civil defence and home affairs typically have responsibility for disaster risk reduction (UNISDR, 2009a).²⁵

A barrier for a more **coherent and holistic approach** to combine Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) and Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR) lies in the diversified regulation, which divides the role and responsibility to deal with climate change, disaster management, or loss of nature. This separation does not take into account the fact that the data interconnects, overlaps or affects each other. This complicates mitigation, response and recovery efforts within and between the sectors of CCA and DRR. In the last decade new EU projects, like e.g. PLACARD (PLATform for Climate Adaptation and Risk reDuction)²⁶ have emerged to connect these communities through dialogue, knowledge exchange and collaboration.

The Sendai Framework (2015–2030)²⁷ provides practitioners with synergising starting points, but increased emphasis and more work is still needed to be put into creating practical solutions to their integration (Gero et al., 2010)²⁸, which must be adequately supported by the local government (EUR-OPA UNISDR, 2011)²⁹. Research has highlighted the **essential role of local governance mechanisms** as the sharp end of the policy wedge, with current examples of proactivity that require to be championed and supported at national level in order to thrive.³⁰

²⁵ https://files.acquia.undp.org/public/migration/ge/GE_isdr_terminology_2009_eng.pdf

²⁶ <https://www.climateurope.eu/9001-2/ PLACARD>

²⁷ <https://www.undrr.org/publication/sendai-framework-disaster-risk-reduction-2015-2030>

²⁸ Gero, Anna, Kristie Meheux, and Dale Dominey-Howes. "Disaster risk reduction and climate change adaptation in the Pacific: The challenge of integration." ATRC-NHRL miscellaneous report 4.3 (2010)

²⁹ https://www.unisdr.org/files/35277_ddrccafinal.pdf

³⁰ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1462901124001084>

SOTERIA has referred to the experience from the Norwegian case (lasting from 2010 to 2020) as a best practice in private-public dialogue and cooperation, which led to the establishment of the Knowledge Bank (2020), where the **insurance sector shares granular loss and damage data**³¹. The long process has given a profound insight into drivers and barriers to the individual stakeholders, and what it finally took to overcome the barriers for sharing these climate-related insurance loss and damage data to national and local public authorities for risk reduction. The insurance actors understood that sharing the data could lead to reducing the risk and improve financial inclusion by allowing the uninsurable to become insurable.

GDPR and the finance regulation on **confidentiality regarding customer relations** was often brought up in these discussions as one of the main legal barriers enabling sharing the insurance data. The regulation on confidentiality, data business sensitivity, see ANNEX I, and the fair of less competition between the insurance actors were main barriers for the insurance data on asset level to be openly available to the public.

For the Knowledge Bank to be able to share the data on asset level with municipalities, the national flood agency and County governor, new regulation was implemented in 2021. The new regulation was also based on dialogue between the insurance association and the Director of civil protection, and came into force in 2021. The regulation requires all insurance companies offering property insurance in Norway to share climate- and disaster risk-related data defined in the regulation (the Civil Protection Act)³².

The Norwegian case and establishment of the national Knowledge Bank has shown that the success factor was **broad multi-stakeholder dialogue from day one**, anchoring process and decisions in top management, clear mandates from the various stakeholders/institution with time and resources to devote to the project, dedicated and motivated people and positivity in building trust between insurance and (especially) municipalities, making common strategies which nudged into new guidelines, routines, and new regulation.

Unfortunately, lack of funding on the side of the Directorate of Civil protection has slowed down or stopped the process of collecting the insurance data. However, the data are still shared (according to the new regulation) monthly from the insurance companies to Finance Norway (the association).

How to overcome the dialogue and mitigation between CCA and DRR communities both on national and local level is (still) a pivotal goal in the EU. EIOPA is presently exploring whether and to what extent insurance value chains should be 'opened' up by

³¹ [Use of insurance loss data by local authorities in Norway | Case studies | Discover the key services, thematic features and tools of Climate-ADAPT Climate-ADAPT](#)

³² [Lov om sivil beskyttelse og beredskap \(sivilbeskyttelsesloven\) - Kapittel V. Kommunal beredskapsplikt - Lovdata](#)

the sharing of insurance-related and specific policyholder data amongst insurance and on-insurance firms, with a view to protect policyholder rights and to allow for innovation in products and services. And it has concluded that a key consideration on possible open insurance solutions is how to find a balance between data protection, insurance, and competition regulations while supporting innovation, efficiency, consumer protection and financial stability³³.

2.6.4 The EU taxonomy – a driver for sharing insurance data.

The EU taxonomy for sustainable finance is a cornerstone of the EU's sustainable finance framework and an important market transparency tool³⁴. It helps direct investments to the economic activities most needed for the transition, in line with the European Green Deal objectives. The regulation entered into force in 2020, and its reporting requirements have applied since 2022. It sets out overarching conditions and criteria for e.g. which non-life insurance economic activity qualifies as environmentally sustainable. An economic activity considered sustainable for non-life insurance companies is sharing of sustainable and climate-related data.

Sharing of insurance loss data for better awareness and climate action is a central part of SOTERIA, and the reason for using the Norwegian case as best practice. Here the insurance sector and its association initiated a multi-stakeholder cooperation starting in 2010 and lasting for 10 years, which led to e.g. a new national data public platform called the Knowledge Bank. The platform is run by the national Civil Protection Agency, which has the right to collect insurance loss data on asset level and share it with local authorities. The data is shared on asset level with defined national and local authorities and otherwise shared with the public on municipality level. The sharing is in line with criterion number 4 on Data sharing in the taxonomy, shown in the box below.³⁵

³³ [Open insurance: accessing and sharing insurance-related data - EIOPA](#)

³⁴ [Regulation - 2020/852 - EN - taxonomy regulation - EUR-Lex](#)

³⁵ [Non-life insurance: underwriting of climate-related perils](#)

Box 1. Non-life insurance: underwriting of climate-related perils (europa.eu)**1. Description**

Provision of the following insurance services (other than life insurance) as defined in Annex I of Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2015/35 of 10 October 2014(670) related to the *underwriting of climate related perils* set out in Appendix A to this Annex:

a) medical expense insurance; b) income protection insurance; c) workers compensation insurance; d) motor vehicle liability insurance; e) other motor insurance; f) marine, aviation and transport insurance; g) fire and other damage to property insurance; h) assistance. The economic activities in this category could be associated with NACE code K65.12 in accordance with the statistical classification of economic activities established by Regulation (EC) No 1893/2006. An economic activity in this category is an enabling activity as referred to in Article 11(1), point (b), of Regulation (EU) 2020/852 where it meets the *technical screening criteria* set out in this section.

4. Data sharing

4.1. With due regard to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament (GDPR) and of the Council (672), *a significant share of loss data related to insurer's activity is made available*, free of charge, to one or several public authorities for the purpose of analytical research. Those public authorities *declare to use the data for purposes of enhancing adaptation to climate change* by the society in a region, country or internationally and the insurer provides the data at a level of granularity sufficient for the use declared by the respective public authorities.

4.2. Where the insurer is not yet sharing such data with a public authority for the aforementioned purpose, it has declared the intention to make its data available, free of charge, to interested third parties and has indicated under which conditions such data can be shared. That declaration of intention to share available data is easily accessible, including on the insurer's website, for relevant public authorities.

Besides EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Finance, the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD)³⁶ is a regulatory driver for sharing data. The Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (hereafter, CSRD), formerly known as the Non-Financial Reporting Directive (NFRD), requires large companies and certain listed SMEs on regulated markets to identify and disclose their material climate impacts, risks, and opportunities related to sustainability, particularly climate change, in a standardized manner. This includes publishing annual sustainability reports covering key environmental, social, and governance (ESG) topics such as climate impacts,

³⁶ [Directive - 2022/2464 - EN - CSRD Directive - EUR-Lex](#)

human rights, and corporate governance practices. By enhancing the consistency and comparability of sustainability data, the CSRD aims to improve corporate transparency and provide investors, regulators, and the public with more reliable information to support informed and responsible decision-making.

Artificial intelligence and telematics will provide new data and can be a driver to understand risk and risk reduction, such as using flood sensors for home insurance. The AI act³⁷ sets out a clear set of risk-based rules for AI developers and deployers regarding specific uses of AI. Digital transformation contributes to closing certain insurance protection gaps and helps increase market transparency, including the development of tools for insurers, distributors and customers to aid them in comparing products and coverage and assessing appropriate price of cover, breaking down barriers for consumers in understanding and assessing insurance.

EU taxonomy regulation on data-sharing and access to new data has created beneficial spill-overs, where data can be re-used to open up significant growth opportunities, or to generate benefits across society in ways that could not be foreseen when the data were first created. Spill-over benefits from insurance data to the public sector as a part of the Norwegian insurance-public cooperation/the Knowledge bank and other similar initiatives, have **motivated and created new research and startups/businesses**, using insurance data in a combination of openly accessible and free of cost public-sector data.

Available studies suggest that data access and sharing can increase the value of data to holders (direct impact), but it can help create 10 to 20 times more value for data users (indirect impact), and 20 to 50 times more value for the wider economy (induced impact).³⁸

In July 2025, the Commission adopted a set of changes and measures to simplify the application of the EU Taxonomy, the CSRD, including the Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS) and the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD).³⁹ This came in response to a **regulatory overload as a barrier** and a concern on the complexity in sustainability regulation and a hinder for **competitiveness** for EU companies. It was first introduced through the EC Omnibus Simplification Package (February 2025), a proposal aimed at streamlining corporate sustainability reporting while maintaining the EU's sustainability goals.

The changes will reduce administrative burden for companies while preserving the framework's core objectives. The simplification measures will apply as of 1 January

³⁷ [Regulation - EU - 2024/1689 - EN - EUR-Lex](#)

³⁸ [Economic and social benefits of data access and sharing: Enhancing Access to and Sharing of Data | OECD](#)

³⁹ [Commission to cut EU taxonomy red tape for companies - Finance](#)

Project Number 101112867

2026 and will cover the 2025 financial year. Although warmly welcomed from most undertakings, many see the benefit to continue to apply their process in measures and reporting according to the regulation as they consider it a benefit for their long-term business policy and the importance of being sustainable.

3. Behavioural Analysis of Barriers (Ecosystem Level)

3.1 Overview - why a behavioural dimension matters?

Addressing climate change adaptation requires more than technological solutions or regulatory reform. It demands **behavioural systems change** at the scale of societies⁴⁰.

The capacity to adapt depends on how institutions, communities, and individuals perceive risks, prioritise actions, and sustain cooperation over time. Behavioral science offers a framework for understanding and influencing these processes by examining the cognitive, social, and structural factors that shape decision-making in real contexts. The advantages of using behavioural insights early in the process of designing or changing new policy approaches and solutions have been recognised on EU level⁴¹.

In this sense, effective adaptation is not only a matter of awareness or capacity but of creating the conditions for collective efficacy and the shared belief among actors that coordinated action will lead to outcomes that are meaningful for the majority of the actors. By applying behavioural insights, we can identify why entrenched routines persist even when better alternatives exist, and how new norms and motivations can be fostered to align daily practices with long-term resilience goals.

Within the specific context of climate-related risk and loss data, behavioural science helps illuminate and guide the transition from fragmented, protective behaviours toward cooperative, data-sharing norms that reflect new climate realities. It enables the design of systems where the smarter, more resilient behaviour becomes the natural default for all actors involved.

Effective recording, collection, storage, and sharing of climate-related **risk** and **loss** data requires **ecosystem change**, not simply the one-time actions of individual organisations. What must shift are patterns and routines across multiple actors within an entire ecosystem (insurers, municipal and national authorities, regulators, scientific bodies, data intermediaries, and, at times, the public). These routines are shaped by a mix of formal forces (mandates, contracts, compliance duties) and informal forces (norms, reciprocity, reputational dynamics). Because climate risk information (forward-looking hazard and exposure signals) and loss information (realised impacts) sit in two adjacent but distinct contexts, behaviours around access, protection, and reuse also

⁴⁰ [Newell, P., Twena, M., & Daley, F. \(2021\). Scaling behaviour change for a 1.5-degree world: challenges and opportunities. *Global Sustainability*, 4, e22.](#)

⁴¹ [Dupoux, M., Gaudeul, A., Baggio, M., BRUNS, H., CIRIOLO, E., KRAWCZYK, M., ... & NOHLEN, H. \(2025\). Unlocking the full potential of behavioural insights for policy.](#)

differ. A behavioural lens clarifies why cooperation stalls and how to unlock sustained, system-level cooperation.

3.2 Four preconditions for change

Successful behavioural change at the ecosystem level, where multiple public and private actors collectively transition to new, cooperative routines of recording, collecting, storing, and sharing climate-related risk and loss data, requires several foundational conditions to be in place. The following analysis of behavioural factors is based on existing literature on behaviour change on systemic level and an analysis of the behaviour change processes observed in the Norwegian Knowledge Bank case, which has been pillar to the efforts around climate risk and loss data. Several defining characteristics become evident and directly inform this study's behavioural framing.

First, this is a case of behaviour change at the ecosystem level - the transition involves a network of interdependent actors, including insurers, public authorities, and intermediaries, rather than isolated individuals. Each operates within shared systems and mutual dependencies, meaning that progress depends on collective shifts, not unilateral action.

Second, the focus is on changing patterns and routines of behaviour, rather than prompting one-off actions. What matters is the establishment of new, stable ways of doing things - new norms, expectations, and interaction models that sustain themselves over time.

Building on behavioural-science evidence⁴² and insights from climate-adaptation research⁴³, four key **preconditions for change** can be identified:

- **Awareness**
- **Motivation**
- **Social/Environmental Pressure, and**
- **Trust**

Together, these conditions describe the psychological and social foundations that must be in place for an entire data ecosystem to transition toward more cooperative, reliable, and adaptive routines for recording, collecting, storing, and sharing climate-related risk and loss data. These factors interact dynamically and must reinforce each other for a behavioural transition to occur and stabilise over time.

⁴² Michie, S., van Stralen, M. M., & West, R. (2011). *The behaviour change wheel: A new method for characterising and designing behaviour change interventions*. *Implementation Science*, 6(42). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1748-5908-6-42>

⁴³ Hauge, Å. L., Flyen, C., Venås, C., Kokkonen, A., & Aall, C. (2020). *Public-Private Cooperation for Climate Adaptation—Providing Insurance Loss Data to the Municipalities*. In *Handbook of climate services* (pp. 157-181). Cham: Springer International Publishing.

3.2.1 Awareness

Awareness is the first and most essential step in any behaviour-change process. It forms the cognitive foundation upon which motivation, pressure, and trust can operate. In the context of climate-related data exchange, awareness must develop simultaneously at several levels across the ecosystem.

- **Awareness of the issue.** All actors, including insurers, public institutions, regulators, and intermediaries, must recognise that the current system for data recording and sharing is fragmented and insufficient. Awareness that “there is a problem” activates the first cognitive step toward change.
- **Awareness of consequences.** Stakeholders must understand the negative outcomes of inaction, including higher adaptation costs, inefficient decision-making, and lost opportunities for prevention. Recognising that limited data sharing generates direct and indirect costs for both individual institutions and society at large creates urgency and ownership of the problem.
- **Awareness of causes.** The different parties involved must share a coherent understanding of why the problem exists. Agreement on a set of *common truths*, for example, that legal ambiguity or the absence of standards are core obstacles, avoids fragmentation of narratives and supports collective solutions. If the reasons for dysfunction are well defined, targeted action (e.g. legal amendments or new data-governance mandates) becomes feasible.
- **Awareness of constraints.** Finally, all actors should be clear about contextual limitations that cannot easily be changed. Examples include national data-protection laws or the fact that certain datasets exist only at national rather than municipal level. Recognising such constraints allows stakeholders to direct resources toward feasible reforms rather than irresolvable barriers.

Without shared awareness at these four levels, coordination remains weak and competing interpretations continue to undermine collective progress.

3.2.2 Motivation

Behavioural change in a multi-actor system occurs only when sufficient motivation exists across key stakeholders. Motivation arises when the perceived **benefits** of new behaviour outweigh the perceived **risks** or **costs**. In this ecosystem, motivation operates differently for insurers, public bodies, and the general public.

Here are motivational forces for the different players:

Insurance companies would not share data if:

- They have a strong sense of ownership because the data has been earned with their own investment of resources and they feel that nobody else is entitled to having this data.
- They fear that sharing this data exposes them to market risks – their competitors can gain an advantage or new competitors can come to the market risking current positions and revenues.
- If it is restricted by the law (or they perceive it so – GDPR).

Insurance companies would share data if:

- They feel that this helps their business and/or contributes to their market position/ performance (revenues).
- This gives them a reputation advantage and relationship benefits with important collaborators in the ecosystem (institutions, clientele, public, media, etc.).
- This is part of the accepted norm in the ecosystem in which they operate and is what their competitors are doing.
- If it is required by the law.

Public entities would not share data if:

- Their mandate requires that they gather and manage this data, and they perceive themselves as owners of the data (legal requirement/mandate).
- They fear that the sharing of data will lead to risks for the public at large, or for certain groups within society.
- They fear that data sharing may influence the market or give an unfair advantage to certain commercial players in a private market.

Public entities would share data if

- Their mandate requires that they disclose or share the specific data (legal requirement/mandate).
- They know that sharing the data will produce benefits that are relevant for them and their role (good publicity, public support, facilitated processes, etc.).
- They are not restricted by the law (even if it does not specifically require that they disclose the data).

The general public is an additional stakeholder in this ecosystem because it can play a role in activating data sharing behavior. The general public can be an active stakeholder in two ways:

- It can be part of the data gathering and sharing. – The public can be active in submitting and providing information about hazards or losses resulting from

natural hazards supplementing official mechanisms through public institutions and insurance companies (i.e. reporting a small landslide along a less used rural road that is not spotted by public institutions and not reported to insurance companies).

- It can be proactive in putting pressure on institutions and insurance companies to be more effective in addressing the changing needs of societies related to the exchange of climate risk and losses data, and meeting the new needs associated with climate related risks.

Across these groups, motivation strengthens when benefits are concrete, visible, and institutionally relevant. Conversely, when benefits remain abstract and risks feel immediate, inertia prevails.

3.2.3 Social and Environmental Pressure

Beyond individual motivation, the wider socio-economic environment has a powerful influence on organisational behaviour. Changing **social norms** within an ecosystem can trigger alignment and sustained behavioural change.⁴⁴

Three mechanisms are particularly relevant:

1. **Peer alignment.** Organisations often benchmark their performance against peers. When leading actors demonstrate successful data collaboration, others tend to follow to avoid reputational loss or to remain competitive.
2. **Emergence of a new normal.** As open and cooperative practices become more common, the perception of what constitutes acceptable behaviour shifts. Sharing data becomes not an exception but the expected norm.
3. **External pressure.** Stakeholders may experience pressure from partners, regulators, and the public to adapt. As societal expectations for climate responsiveness grow, maintaining restrictive or siloed practices becomes increasingly untenable.

Insights from environmental psychology reinforce this perspective: social proof and normative feedback loops are strong behavioural drivers, often more effective than

⁴⁴ [Hauge, Å. L., Flyen, C., Venås, C., Kokkonen, A., & Aall, C. \(2020\). Public-Private Cooperation for Climate Adaptation—Providing Insurance Loss Data to the Municipalities. In *Handbook of climate services* \(pp. 157-181\). Cham: Springer International Publishing.](#)

formal regulation alone⁴⁵. Visible examples of collaboration help redefine what is normal and desirable, accelerating systemic change⁴⁶.

3.2.4 Trust

Trust is the final and indispensable precondition for sustained behavioural change. Even when awareness, motivation, and social pressure are present, actors will not engage in open data sharing if they distrust their partners, the system, or its fairness. Trust reduces perceived risk, encourages reciprocity, and transforms one-off compliance into habitual cooperation.

Trust must operate on three interconnected dimensions:

1. **Trust in partners.** Participants must believe that other actors in the ecosystem will use data responsibly and uphold agreed commitments
2. **Trust in the system.** Confidence in the integrity, security, and reliability of data-management mechanisms is critical. Stakeholders need assurance that data are stored, processed, and accessed according to transparent, jointly defined protocols.
3. **Trust in fairness.** All actors must perceive the system as equitable, where benefits and responsibilities are shared fairly. When reciprocity and equal treatment are evident, cooperation becomes self-reinforcing.

Empirical findings support this conclusion: initiatives where losses are clearly visualised and shared have been shown to increase political and organisational engagement, while high data quality and precision strengthen institutional credibility and trust in outcomes. Trust is therefore **non-negotiable** as it is the glue that holds multi-actor collaboration together and the condition without which no behavioural or systemic transition can be sustained.

In summary, the transition toward effective, routine, and equitable data-sharing practices for climate-related risk and loss information depends on simultaneous progress across these four preconditions. Awareness creates a shared understanding of the problem and its boundaries; motivation provides the energy for change; social and environmental pressures reinforce emerging norms; and trust ensures durability

⁴⁵ Nyborg, K., Anderies, J. M., Dannenberg, A., Lindahl, T., Schill, C., Schlüter, M., ... de Zeeuw, A. (2016). *Social norms as solutions: Policies may influence large-scale behavioral tipping*. *Science*, 354(6308), 42–43. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aaf9072>

⁴⁶ Steg, L., & Vlek, C. (2009). *Encouraging pro-environmental behaviour: An integrative review and research agenda*. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 29(3), 309–317. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2008.10.004>

and depth of cooperation. Together, these preconditions define the behavioural infrastructure necessary for a resilient, adaptive, and collaborative data ecosystem.

3.3 Understanding System Change

For the purposes of this analysis, the **COM-B model** (*Capability, Opportunity, Motivation - Behaviour*)⁴⁷ was selected as the most relevant and applicable framework for understanding behavioural barriers and drivers in the context of climate-related risk and loss data. The model provides a structured lens to identify the interacting factors that influence how organisations and systems behave. It recognises that behaviour change at an ecosystem level requires more than awareness or technical capacity: it depends on the alignment of capabilities, enabling opportunities, and sustained motivation across all actors. COM-B is therefore well suited to analysing this context, as it helps clarify why certain behavioural patterns persist despite favourable conditions, and how targeted interventions can enable the transition from fragmented and reactive practices to stable, repeatable routines of data recording, collection, storage, and sharing that underpin effective climate adaptation.

3.3.1 Capability

Capability encompasses the organisational skills, resources, and clarity of roles required to carry out data-related tasks. In this ecosystem, it refers to:

- **Technical and legal literacy** – the ability to interpret data-protection rules (e.g., GDPR), sectoral confidentiality clauses, and permissible forms of anonymisation or aggregation;
- **Operational competence** – skills and standard operating procedures (SOPs) for curating loss datasets, conducting quality assurance (QA/QC), versioning, and producing metadata; and
- **Role clarity** – designated data stewards and clearly defined “single points of truth” who maintain responsibility for accuracy and timeliness.

Without these capabilities, even motivated actors cannot perform or sustain the required behaviours.

⁴⁷ Michie, S., van Stralen, M. M., & West, R. (2011). *The behaviour change wheel: A new method for characterising and designing behaviour change interventions*. *Implementation Science*, 6(42). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1748-5908-6-42>

3.3.2 Opportunity

Opportunity refers to the **external physical and social conditions** that enable behaviour.

- **Physical opportunity** includes the existence of secure data-exchange channels, standard data-sharing agreements, effective access models, stable funding mechanisms, and interoperable tools that make routine sharing feasible and efficient.
- **Social opportunity** captures the surrounding environment of norms and relationships: expectations of reciprocity, visible peer examples, trust between sectors, and the influence of professional working groups and communities of practice (CoPs) that model and normalise collaborative behaviour.

These physical and social dimensions jointly determine whether data-sharing routines can be established and maintained over time.

3.3.3 Motivation

Motivation includes both **conscious processes** (conscious cost-benefit evaluation, strategic priorities) and **subconscious processes** (habits, norms, and emotional drivers). In this context it entails:

- **Perceived benefits and risks** – whether actors believe that sharing data will yield meaningful gains (e.g., better risk pricing, improved adaptation budgets) or expose them to competitive, political, or reputational harm;
- **Cognitive biases** such as *status-quo bias* and *loss aversion*, which favour maintaining familiar practices over adopting new norms of behaviour;
- **Reputational and mission alignment** – the degree to which data sharing supports institutional goals or enhances public credibility; and
- **Habit formation** – the embedding of sharing routines (e.g., regular uploads, fixed reporting cycles) that make collaboration self-sustaining.

Within this framework, the COM-B model is used to **map existing behavioural barriers** and **identify drivers and intervention levers** that can build stable, repeatable routines rather than sporadic data exchanges. The focus is on creating the conditions for enduring **ecosystem-level behaviour change**, where improved cooperation around both *risk* and *loss* data becomes the default operating mode.

3.4 Applying the COM-B Model to Climate-Related Data Sharing

The **COM-B model** identifies three key conditions that shape human behaviour: **Capability**, **Opportunity**, and **Motivation**. These three factors interact to determine whether a particular behaviour, i.e. recording, collecting, storing, and sharing climate-related risk and loss data, can take hold and become routine.

- **Capability** refers to the psychological understanding and practical ability to perform a behaviour.
- **Opportunity** captures the external conditions that make a behaviour possible or easier to carry out.
- **Motivation** includes both the conscious decisions and automatic habits that drive people to act or to keep doing things the way they have always done them.

Using this model, we can identify what needs to be in place for **all key actors**, including: insurance companies, public institutions and organisations, businesses, and local residents, to participate more actively and willingly in the exchange of climate-related data that benefits the whole community.

3.4.1 Capability

Knowledge and skills

All participants need to understand *why* climate-related risk and loss data matter and *how* they contribute to better collective decisions. Insurers, local authorities, and businesses should recognise how accurate data can support smarter planning, investment, and risk reduction, while residents can benefit from greater awareness of local vulnerabilities. This understanding must be matched with practical capability, such as: the ability to collect, aggregate, interpret, and, where necessary, anonymise data responsibly.

Technical and organisational capacity

Robust systems are required to manage and share information securely while maintaining data integrity and privacy. For institutions, this may mean having appropriate databases and protocols but also staff members with the needed skills to operate them. For local communities, it may mean user-friendly reporting tools that make participation easy. This capacity can be built through targeted training, technical assistance, and simplified digital tools as it is a precondition for reliable, confident data exchange.

3.4.2 Opportunity

Supportive frameworks

Clear regulations, standards, and procedures are needed to make data sharing possible and safe. Transparent rules defining who can access which information, and under what conditions, help reduce uncertainty and build confidence. Incentives such as recognition schemes or access to shared resources can encourage participation.

Collaboration mechanisms

Partnerships between insurers, government bodies, research organisations, and community groups can create a shared sense of purpose. Collaborative platforms or “knowledge hubs” allow actors to exchange information and experience, fostering trust and reciprocity.

Financial and resource incentives

Economic mechanisms, such as reduced fees, tax advantages, or co-funded infrastructure, can motivate participation. Likewise, when data sharing leads to more efficient spending or reduced losses, the resulting savings act as a reinforcing incentive.

3.4.3 Motivation

Awareness of benefits

Actors are more likely to share data when they understand how it serves both public and private interests. Insurers can improve risk pricing and lower losses; local governments can justify stronger adaptation budgets; businesses can anticipate disruptions; and residents can make safer decisions.

Social and market expectations

As awareness of climate risks grows, so do expectations for transparency and collaboration. Public opinion, peer examples, and professional norms can all generate pressure to act responsibly and share information for the common good.

Reputation and recognition

Positive visibility for participating in open, climate-smart data practices can motivate institutions and businesses. When collaboration is publicly acknowledged—through awards, certifications, or local success stories—it strengthens both pride and commitment to continue.

For effective data sharing to become a **normal and sustained practice**, all three behavioural conditions must align.

- **Capability** requires that actors have the knowledge, skills, and systems to handle data responsibly.
- **Opportunity** means that enabling structures, incentives, and collaboration frameworks are in place.
- **Motivation** ensures that actors see clear benefits, feel social support, and gain recognition for their contribution.

When these three elements reinforce one another, behaviour change shifts from isolated initiatives to **collective, routine action** building the trust and cooperation needed for smarter, more resilient responses to climate risk.

4. Combining PESTEL and COM-B to Understand Realities

4.1 Overview

Understanding the drivers and barriers to effective climate-related risk and loss data sharing requires examining not only the structural and regulatory context in which stakeholders operate but also the human and behavioural dynamics that shape how they act within it. While the PESTEL framework provides a structured overview of the *tangible, systemic conditions*, i.e. political, economic, sociocultural, technological, environmental, and legal factors, the COM-B model complements it by revealing the *intangible, behavioural mechanisms* that determine how these external conditions translate into actual behaviour.

Overlaying these two perspectives allows for a more complete understanding of the data-sharing environment. Objective factors such as governance frameworks, legal mandates, or infrastructure may define what is possible in principle, but behavioural factors such as trust, motivation, social norms, and perceived risk, determine what happens in practice. Bringing these two layers together clarifies where barriers exist and also why they persist despite seemingly favourable conditions.

4.2 A matrix for joint PESTEL/COM-B analysis

The combined analysis presented in this section therefore integrates insights from both models to produce a **joint analytical matrix**. This matrix aligns each PESTEL dimension with the corresponding behavioural determinants identified through the COM-B model. The result is a diagnostic tool that captures **how structural enablers and behavioural forces interact** to either facilitate or hinder effective data recording, collection, storage, and sharing.

Fig. 2: A PESTEL/COM-B Analytical Matrix - Template Illustration

COM-B \ PESTEL Capability	Political	Economic	Social	Technological	Environmental	Legal
Knowledge & skills	●●	○○	●○	●○	●○	●●
Technical infrastructure	○○	○○	●○	●●	N/A	○○

Opportunity	Political	Economic	Social	Technological	Environmental	Legal
Regulatory environment	●●	●○	●○	●○	N/A	●●
Collaboration mechanisms	●○	●○	●○	●○	N/A	●○
Financial incentives	●○	●●	N/A	●○	N/A	●○

Motivation	Political	Economic	Social	Technological	Environmental	Legal
Awareness of benefits	●○	●●	●●	●○	●●	●○
Market pressure	●○	●○	●○	●○	●●	N/A
Reputational considerations	○○	●●	●●	○○	●●	N/A

Legend: ●● = solid
 ●○ = inconsistent
 ○○ = lacking

4.3 PESTEL/COM-B analysis of three case studies

By applying this integrated framework to three regional case studies within the SOTERIA project - Gabrovo (Bulgaria), Valencia (Spain), and Trøndelag (Norway) - we can compare how different political, economic, and social contexts shape stakeholder behaviour and collaboration patterns. Each matrix in this section highlights the key barriers currently influencing data management dynamics in the respective region, illustrating both the systemic constraints and the behavioural realities that need to be addressed to enable efficient, trustworthy, and sustainable data exchange.

Together, these matrices form the basis for identifying targeted actions - policy adjustments, institutional reforms, or behavioural interventions - that can bridge the gap between what is technically possible and what is behaviourally achievable in advancing smart climate-risk data ecosystems.

4.2.1. Gabrovo

The PESTEL/COM-B matrix for **Gabrovo (Bulgaria)** captures a context characterised by low institutional maturity and fragmented capacities for climate risk and loss data management. The analysis reveals that most barriers are structural—stemming from unclear mandates, lack of investment in skills and infrastructure, and the absence of legal or financial incentives for collaboration. At the same time, behavioural barriers such as limited awareness, weak motivation, and minimal trust across institutions further constrain progress. Despite increasing climate impacts that raise awareness of risk, these pressures have not yet translated into coordinated action or data-driven decision-making. The matrix highlights the need to build both capability and motivation across public institutions, private actors, and the general public to create the foundation for systematic data exchange.

COM-B Model Barrier Categories	POLITICAL (governance)	ECONOMIC	SOCIAL	TECHNOLOGICAL	ENVIRONMENTAL	LEGAL
Capability - knowledge & skills	Inconsistent Understanding the importance of climate risk data sharing on the political level. <i>There is some understanding on the national/ regional</i>	Lack Investment in knowledge/ skills needed for climate risk data sharing. <i>There is no targeted investment in skills and capacity building as there</i>	Lack General public awareness of the importance (value) of climate risk data-sharing. <i>The general public is completely unaware of the</i>	Inconsistent Human capacity/ skills for processing/ analysing/ sharing. <i>There are very skilled experts who are capable of sharing, processing, and analysing data, but not specific to</i>	Solid Environmental/ weather events that make climate risk prominent. <i>Natural disasters and damage from them are increasingly frequent, and that makes society aware of them, but not that</i>	Lack Legal obligation to develop and maintain capacity in climate risk data sharing. <i>There is no mature awareness on the social level that can translate into recognition.</i>

<p>technical infrastructure</p>	<p><i>government level, but it is limited and not focused on data sharing.</i></p> <p>Inconsistent</p> <p>Available mechanisms for accessing/ using climate risk data at the political (government) level. <i>There are entities that have climate risk-related data but there are no established or consistent processes for accessing and</i></p>	<p><i>are no targeted efforts to enable such data sharing.</i></p> <p>Inconsistent</p> <p>Investment in the establishment/ maintenance of data-sharing infrastructure. <i>The state has made and continues to invest in the creation and maintenance of climate monitoring/ modelling data but it does not use and operationalise them for policies</i></p>	<p><i>importance and need for climate risk data as there is no education/ information that can make people more aware.</i></p> <p>Lack</p> <p>Available mechanisms for public access (use) of data on climate risks. <i>There is no mechanism and there is no understanding that public access is valuable.</i></p>	<p><i>climate risk.</i></p> <p>Inconsistent</p> <p>Technological infrastructure to enable the flow of data (incl. unification between data sources and formats). <i>The information systems exist, but there is no unification and connection between them.</i></p>	<p><i>climate risk data can be one of the important ways of increasing preparedness and mitigating risks and damage.</i></p> <p>N/A</p>	<p>Lack</p> <p>Legal obligation to create/ use climate risk data exchange infrastructure. <i>There is no legal obligation to create and use climate risk data.</i></p>
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	<i>using it to guide decision-making.</i>	<i>and decision making.</i>				
<p>Opportunity</p> <p>- regulatory environment</p>	<p>Inconsistent</p> <p>Policies that prioritise climate action and incentivise climate risk data exchange <i>Some policies prioritise climate action, but they are not focused on climate risk data.</i></p>	<p>Lack</p> <p>Economic/ market advantages for using/ sharing climate risk data <i>There is no use of data, so it is not a competitive advantage.</i></p>	<p>Lack</p> <p>High social support for climate action and climate risk data sharing policies <i>There is no awareness about the need for climate risk data.</i></p>	<p>Lack</p> <p>Policies that encourage investment in or the use of existing infrastructure for climate risk data exchange. <i>There are no policies due to the lack of awareness that this is needed.</i></p>	N/A	<p>Inconsistent</p> <p>Legislation is clear and facilitates climate risk data exchange. <i>There is legislation that requires data gathering, but it is not enforced.</i></p>
<p>- collaboration mechanisms</p>	<p>Inconsistent</p> <p>Policies that favor collaboration between</p>	<p>Lack</p> <p>Existing collaboration that reduces the costs of collecting,</p>	<p>Lack</p> <p>There are social expectations (norms) for</p>	<p>Inconsistent</p> <p>Existing technologies that enable/ facilitate collaboration</p>	N/A	<p>Inconsistent</p> <p>Legislation that enables collaboration among different data holders/ users</p>

<p>financial incentives</p>	<p>institutions and/ or public/ private collaboration for data exchange <i>Policy document outlines collaboration, but there are no practical mechanisms that operationalise it.</i></p> <p>Lack</p> <p>Policies that create financial incentives for contributions to climate risk data exchange. <i>There are no such policies.</i></p>	<p>maintaining, and managing data on climate risks <i>It does not exist in reality.</i></p> <p>Lack</p> <p>Financial benefits/ incentives (i.e, tax incentives) for climate risk data sharing/ using. <i>There are no such benefits/ incentives.</i></p>	<p>contributing to/ supporting climate data risk exchange <i>There is a lack of awareness that this is needed.</i></p> <p>N/A</p>	<p>among different owners/ users of climate risk data <i>Technology and expertise exist, but there are no linkages to enable collaboration.</i></p> <p>Lack</p> <p>Using technological infrastructure produces financial incentives for participants. <i>Technological infrastructure exists, but it is not used for climate risk data sharing.</i></p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p><i>There are provisions in the legislation for collaboration but they are not enforced in practice.</i></p> <p>N/A</p>
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<p>Motivation</p> <p>awareness of benefits</p> <p>market pressure</p>	<p>Lack</p> <p>Understanding of the benefits for society/ ecosystem. <i>Only vague provisions and generic commitments at the political level, and benefits are not discussed.</i></p> <p>Lack</p> <p>Policies that</p>	<p>Lack</p> <p>Awareness/ transparent access to information about whether an entity participates in climate risk data sharing. <i>No entities use or share climate risk data.</i></p> <p>Lack</p> <p>Economic</p>	<p>Lack</p> <p>Social recognition for participation in climate risk data exchange. <i>There is no exchange so no social recognition.</i></p> <p>Lack</p> <p>Social pressure</p>	<p>Inconsistent</p> <p>Awareness of the benefits of participating in climate risk data sharing. <i>Some individual professionals and entities have some understanding, but there is no established common vision as to what this could look like.</i></p> <p>Lack</p> <p>Market pressure to</p>	<p>Inconsistent</p> <p>Frequency and/or recency and/ or impact scale of weather/ environmental disasters that activate awareness on the benefits of participating in climate risk data exchange. <i>Climate disasters are ever more frequent which increase understanding of climate risks and that they need to be addressed but that does not immediately translate into understanding about the role of climate risk data sharing.</i></p> <p>Inconsistent</p> <p>Frequency and/or</p>	<p>Lack</p> <p>Awareness of the legal benefits of participating in climate risk data sharing. <i>There are no legal benefits.</i></p> <p>N/A</p>
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<p>reputational considerations</p>	<p>create market pressure/ incentives for climate risk data exchange. <i>No such policies exist.</i></p> <p>Inconsistent</p> <p>Reputational benefits for policies favoring climate risk</p>	<p>benefits for participating in an exchange of data. <i>No such benefits exist as there is no exchange of data in the marketplace.</i></p> <p>Lack</p> <p>Reputational incentives/ benefits in the market for participating in</p>	<p>to participate in climate risk data exchange. <i>There is no awareness on the social level to lead to pressure.</i></p> <p>Lack</p> <p>Social recognition for participation in climate risk data exchange.</p>	<p>invest in/ use climate risk data exchange technology. <i>There is no understanding of the necessity to exchange climate risk data that can lead to market pressure.</i></p> <p>Lack</p> <p>Reputational (market) incentives for participating in technical mechanisms for</p>	<p>recency and/ or impact scale of weather/ environmental disasters make participation in climate risk data sharing a requirement for the market. <i>Climate disasters are ever more frequent, which increases understanding of climate risks and that they need to be addressed, but that does not immediately translate into understanding about the role of climate risk data sharing.</i></p> <p>Lack</p> <p>Reputational (market) incentives for participation. <i>There is no mature awareness on the</i></p>	<p>N/A</p>
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	<p>data exchange. <i>General climate policies bring some reputational benefits, but this is at an early stage of maturity and not related to climate risk data.</i></p>	<p>climate risk data exchange. <i>There is no maturity in understanding the value that can translate into reputational benefits.</i></p>	<p><i>There is no mature awareness on the social level that can translate into recognition.</i></p>	<p>data exchange <i>There is no mature awareness on the social level that can translate into recognition.</i></p>	<p><i>social level that can translate into recognition.</i></p>	
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4.2.2. Valencia

The PESTEL/COM-B matrix for Valencia (Spain) illustrates a context with relatively advanced legal and institutional frameworks but fragmented coordination and uneven motivation among actors. Strong legislation on climate action and flood risk management provides a solid foundation, yet these mandates are not consistently operationalised across governance levels. Economic and behavioural barriers persist, including limited financial incentives, weak collaboration between public and private entities, and low public awareness of the value of data sharing. Despite the availability of rich climate and insurance data, technical integration and cultural readiness for open exchange remain limited. The matrix underscores the importance of translating Valencia’s strong regulatory base into practical mechanisms, shared standards, and clearer incentives to convert awareness into sustained behavioural change.

COM-B Model Barrier Categories	POLITICAL (governance)	ECONOMIC	SOCIAL	TECHNOLOGICAL	ENVIRONMENTAL	LEGAL
Capability - knowledge & skills	Solid Understanding the importance of climate risk data sharing on the political level. Inconsistent <i>Opportunities for a better coordination</i>	Inconsistent Investment in knowledge/ skills needed for climate risk data sharing. <i>There is some investment supporting capacity building.</i>	Lack General public awareness of the importance (value) of climate risk data-sharing. <i>The general public does not hold any awareness of</i>	Inconsistent Human capacity/ skills for processing/ analysing/ sharing. <i>There is a significant amount of public information but this information is not linked.</i>	Solid Environmental/ weather events that make climate risk prominent. <i>At the national level AEMET, SAIH and at regional level AVAMET,</i>	Solid Legal obligation to perform risk assessment. <i>In Spain, municipalities at medium or high flood risk are obligated to conduct flood risk assessments as part of their municipal action planning. This</i>

<p>- technical infrastructure</p>	<p><i>across governance levels.</i></p> <p>Inconsistent Available mechanisms for accessing/ using climate risk data at the political (government) level. <i>Some technical infrastructure exists to support data exchange.</i></p>	<p>Inconsistent Investment in the establishment/ maintenance of data-sharing infrastructure. <i>Some investment supports existing technical infrastructure and its expansion.</i></p>	<p><i>the importance of data in this context.</i></p> <p>Inconsistent Available mechanisms for public access (use) of data on climate risks but there is a lack of public awareness of these platforms.</p>	<p>Lack Technological infrastructure to enable the flow of data (incl. unification between data sources and formats). <i>There is lack of technological solutions.</i></p>	<p><i>obligation is based on the Spanish regulatory framework for flood risk management, which in turn is grounded in European legal frameworks. The specific regulations and procedures are detailed in the Royal Decree 903/2010, which also outlines how to assess and manage flood risks.</i></p> <p><i>By law insurance policies must include coverage for extraordinary risks.</i></p> <p><i>The total amount of insured losses is fully known for extraordinary risks by the CCS.</i></p> <p><i>The total insured value (exposure) is also known, since the</i></p>
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						<p><i>system applies to all insurance policies in the country.</i></p> <p><i>The loss data originates from the claims management process by private insurance companies, from which relevant information is extracted for digital processing.</i></p>
<p>Opportunity</p> <p>regulatory environment</p>	<p>Lack</p> <p>Policies that prioritise climate action and incentivise climate risk data exchange <i>No targeted policies are in place.</i></p>	<p>Lack</p> <p>Economic/ market advantages for using/ sharing climate risk data <i>No market advantages encouraging climate risk data sharing.</i></p> <p>Solid</p>	<p>Lack</p> <p>High social support for climate action and climate risk data sharing policies <i>There is lack of social support.</i></p>	<p>Inconsistent</p> <p>Policies that encourage investment in or the use of existing infrastructure for climate risk data exchange. <i>Some policies incentivise investment.</i></p>	N/A	<p>Inconsistent</p> <p>Legislation is clear and facilitates climate risk data exchange. <i>The legislation is not consistent and clear.</i></p>

<p>collaboration mechanisms</p>	<p>Inconsistent Policies that favor collaboration between institutions and/ or public/ private collaboration for data exchange <i>There are no practical policy mechanisms.</i></p>	<p>Insurance coverage Lack Existing collaboration that reduces the costs of collecting, maintaining, and managing data on climate risks <i>There are no practical policy mechanisms.</i></p>	<p>Lack There are social expectations (norms) for contributing to/ supporting climate data risk exchange <i>There is no social awareness at all.</i></p>	<p>Inconsistent Existing technologies that enable/ facilitate collaboration among different owners/ users of climate risk data <i>Some are in place.</i></p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Inconsistent Legislation that enables collaboration among different data holders/ users</p>
<p>financial incentives</p>	<p>Lack Policies that create financial incentives for contributions to climate risk data exchange. <i>There are no such policies.</i></p>	<p>Lack Financial benefits/ incentives (i.e., tax incentives) for climate risk data sharing/ using. <i>Funding for data sharing infrastructure is not in place.</i></p>		<p>Lack Using technological infrastructure produces financial incentives for participants. <i>Some granular climate and loss data is available. The CCS has the</i></p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>

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				<i>information at zipcode but the availability of RVA tools</i>		
Motivation						
- awareness of benefits	Inconsistent Understanding of the benefits for society/ ecosystem. <i>There is some but largely inconsistent.</i>	Inconsistent Awareness/ transparent access to information about whether an entity participates in climate risk data sharing. <i>There is limited awareness.</i>	Lack Social recognition for participation in climate risk data exchange. <i>There is no recognition among the public.</i>	Lack Awareness of the benefits of participating in climate risk data sharing. <i>Benefits are not widely recognised.</i>	Inconsistent Frequency and/or impact scale of weather/ environmental disasters that activate awareness on the benefits of participating in climate risk data exchange. <i>There is some awareness.</i>	Inconsistent Awareness of the legal benefits of participating in climate risk data sharing. <i>There is limited awareness on the legal aspects guiding climate risk data sharing.</i>
- market pressure	Lack Policies that create market pressure/ incentives for climate risk data exchange. <i>There are no relevant</i>	Lack Economic benefits for participating in an exchange of data. <i>There are no incentives from the market.</i>	Lack Social pressure to participate in climate risk data exchange. <i>There is zero pressure.</i>	Lack Market pressure to invest in/ use climate risk data exchange technology. <i>No market pressures.</i>	Lack Frequency and/or recency and/ or impact scale of weather/ environmental disasters make participation in climate risk data sharing a	N/A

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<p>reputational consideration</p>	<p><i>policies in place.</i></p> <p>Inconsistent Reputational benefits for policies favoring climate risk data exchange. <i>Some in place.</i></p>	<p>Inconsistent Reputational incentives/ benefits in the market for participating in climate risk data exchange. <i>Some reputational gains exist.</i></p>	<p>Lack Social recognition for participation in climate risk data exchange. <i>There is no recognition that motivates participation.</i></p>	<p>Inconsistent Reputational (market) incentives for participating in technical mechanisms for data exchange <i>There are some benefits that incentivise participation.</i></p>	<p>requirement for the market. <i>There is no market requirement.</i></p> <p>Lack Reputational (market) incentives for participation. <i>There is no market incentive.</i></p>	<p>N/A</p>
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3.2.3. Trøndelag

The PESTEL/COM-B matrix for Trøndelag (Norway) demonstrates a mature governance environment supported by robust legal obligations, advanced digital infrastructure, and well-established mechanisms for risk data management. However, the analysis shows that even in a well-developed system, behavioural and motivational barriers continue to limit full collaboration. Institutional silos, inconsistent interpretation of rules, and limited financial incentives prevent actors from turning technical capability into routine practice. Trust, coordination, and shared purpose remain critical for advancing from compliance-based data sharing to proactive, learning-oriented collaboration. The Trøndelag case highlights that structural readiness must be matched by behavioural enablers—such as peer networks, transparency, and shared value frameworks—to sustain ecosystem-level change.

COM-B Model Barrier Categories	POLITICAL (governance)	ECONOMIC	SOCIAL	TECHNOLOGICAL	ENVIRONMENTAL	LEGAL
Capability - knowledge & skills	Inconsistent Understanding the importance of climate risk data sharing on the political level. <i>Coordination across governance levels: rules exist, but</i>	Inconsistent Investment in knowledge/ skills needed for climate risk data sharing. <i>Several networks support competence and knowledge exchange (e.g. KS, iFront network of the</i>	Inconsistent General public awareness of the importance (value) of climate risk data-sharing. <i>There is no registry of damage to self-insured assets.</i>	Inconsistent Human capacity/ skills for processing/ analysing/ sharing. <i>There is no registry of damage to self-insured assets.</i>	Solid Environmental/ weather events that make climate risk prominent. <i>Growing number of weather events make climate risk very obvious.</i>	Solid Legal obligation to develop and maintain capacity for climate risk data sharing <i>through the public map database (DOK) under the Planning and Building Act.</i> <i>There is legal obligation to perform RVA under the Planning and</i>

<p>technical infrastructure</p>	<p><i>municipalities face challenges in interpreting and translating them into practice.</i></p> <p>Inconsistent <i>Available mechanisms for accessing/ using climate risk data at the political (government) level. National and regional authorities use well-developed data infrastructures (e.g., DOK</i></p>	<p><i>largest cities, and the regional initiative Nettverk klimatilpassing Trøndelag), though their contributions vary.</i></p> <p>Inconsistent <i>Investment in the establishment/ maintenance of data-sharing infrastructure. Stable funding for core systems exists, but smaller municipalities face resource gaps to maintain or upgrade infrastructure and data</i></p>	<p>Solid <i>Available mechanisms for public access (use) of data on climate risks. Technical systems are available. There is no registry of damage to self-insured assets.</i></p>	<p>Inconsistent <i>Technological infrastructure to enable the flow of data (incl. unification between data sources and formats). Strong digital infrastructure is in place; integration between datasets (insurance, planning, hazards) is incomplete.</i></p>	<p><i>Building Act and the Civil Protection Act. There is a legal obligation to share insurance loss data under the Knowledge Bank Regulation but there is lack of placement responsibility.</i></p> <p>Inconsistent <i>Legal obligation to create/ use climate risk data exchange infrastructure. Some legal mechanisms require maintaining and sharing data.</i></p>
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	<i>database, NVEs systems), but municipalities vary in how effectively they use or connect to them.</i>	<i>management tools.</i>				
Opportunity regulatory environment	Inconsistent Policies that prioritise climate action and incentivise climate risk data exchange <i>National and regional policy frameworks mandate data collection and risk assessment but coordination between</i>	Solid Economic/ market advantages for using/ sharing climate risk data, <i>illustrated by the growing number of insurance products that reward climate adaptation measures. There is solid insurance coverage.</i>	Inconsistent Social support for climate action and climate risk data sharing policies <i>Regulations recognise public right to access environmental information, but there is limited public awareness and social pressure.</i>	Lack Policies that encourage investment in or the use of existing infrastructure for climate risk data exchange. <i>Regulations encourage digitalisation but implementation in municipalities is not systematic.</i>		Inconsistent Legislation is clear and facilitates climate risk data exchange. <i>The legal framework requires data generation, sharing, and access but public and private collaboration is still inconsistent.</i>

<p>collaboration mechanisms</p>	<p><i>municipalities and agencies varies in practice.</i></p> <p>Inconsistent Policies that favor collaboration between institutions and/ or public/ private collaboration for data exchange <i>Formal networks and partnerships exist but coordination between sectors remains inconsistent.</i></p>	<p>Lack Existing collaboration that reduces the costs of collecting, maintaining, and managing data on climate risks <i>Cost-sharing mechanisms for data collection or platform maintenance are very limited.</i></p>	<p>Lack There are social expectations (norms) for contributing to/ supporting climate data risk exchange <i>There is lack of systematic collaboration.</i></p>	<p>Inconsistent Existing technologies that enable/ facilitate collaboration among different owners/ users of climate risk data <i>Shared digital platforms exist but there are differences in data standards and metadata practices.</i></p>		<p>Inconsistent Legislation that enables collaboration among different data holders/ users <i>There is legal mandate for public-private data sharing on losses but collaboration varies.</i></p>
<p>financial incentives</p>	<p>Lack Policies that</p>	<p>Lack Financial</p>		<p>Lack Using technological</p>		

	<p>create financial incentives for contributions to climate risk data exchange. <i>No direct policy mechanisms are in place for municipalities.</i></p>	<p>benefits/ incentives (i.e., tax incentives) for climate risk data sharing/ using. <i>There is lack of funding for data sharing infrastructure.</i></p>		<p>infrastructure produces financial incentives for participants. <i>There is inconsistent granular climate data available; granular loss data available + available RVA tools.</i></p>		
<p>Motivation</p> <p>- awareness of benefits</p>	<p>Inconsistent Understanding of the benefits for society/ ecosystem. <i>Policymakers recognise the value of data but awareness remains uneven.</i></p>	<p>Lack Awareness/ transparent access to information about whether an entity participates in climate risk data sharing. <i>Policymakers recognise the value of data-driven decision-</i></p>	<p>Inconsistent Social recognition for participation in climate risk data exchange. <i>Awareness among the general public of the societal benefits of climate risk</i></p>	<p>Inconsistent Awareness of the benefits of participating in climate risk data sharing. <i>Awareness among the general public of the societal benefits of climate risk and loss data remains limited.</i></p>	<p>Solid Frequency and/or recency and/ or impact scale of weather/ environmental disasters that activate awareness on the benefits of participating in climate risk data exchange. <i>Frequent floods and extreme weather events strengthen</i></p>	<p>Inconsistent Awareness of the legal benefits of participating in climate risk data sharing.</p>

<p>market pressure</p>	<p>Solid Policies that create market pressure/ incentives for climate risk data exchange. <i>Limited direct market pressure on public authorities</i></p>	<p><i>making for climate adaptation, but awareness remains uneven across administrative levels; many local governments still see data sharing as a technical task rather than a strategic tool.</i></p> <p>Lack Economic benefits for participating in an exchange of data. <i>There is lack of market pressure.</i></p>	<p><i>and loss data remains limited.</i></p> <p>Lack Social pressure to participate in climate risk data exchange. <i>There is no social demand for transparency around climate risk data.</i></p>	<p>Inconsistent Market pressure to invest in/ use climate risk data exchange technology. <i>Some pressure to modernise data systems with uneven uptake.</i></p>	<p><i>public awareness.</i></p> <p>Inconsistent Frequency and/or recency and/ or impact scale of weather/ environmental disasters make participation in climate risk data sharing a requirement for the market.</p>	<p>N/A</p>
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<p>reputational considerations</p>	<p>Inconsistent Reputational benefits for policies favoring climate risk data exchange. <i>Recognition remains informal and largely internal to professional networks.</i></p>	<p>Inconsistent Reputational incentives/benefits in the market for participating in climate risk data exchange. <i>Reputational gains do not translate into clear market advantages.</i></p>	<p>Inconsistent Social recognition for participation in climate risk data exchange. <i>Public awareness of who contributes to data sharing is limited and reputational rewards are minimal.</i></p>	<p>Inconsistent Reputational (market) incentives for participating in technical mechanisms for data exchange <i>Some are in place but not systematic.</i></p>	<p>Lack Reputational (market) incentives for participation. <i>There is lack of any.</i></p>	
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5. Discussion: Understanding Barriers and Drivers Through the Combined PESTEL–COM-B Lens

The combined **PESTEL–COM-B matrix** provides a comprehensive view of the barriers and drivers that shape the ability and willingness of different actors to record, collect, store, and share climate-related risk and loss data. By integrating structural analysis (PESTEL) with behavioural insight (COM-B), it reveals not only what conditions exist but also how they interact to enable or block effective data exchange.

Across the three regional cases - **Gabrovo (Bulgaria)**, **Valencia (Spain)**, and **Trøndelag (Norway)** - the combined approach exposes a spectrum of maturity:

- Gabrovo represents an early-stage context where both structural and behavioural preconditions for data sharing remain weak.
- Valencia illustrates a more developed setting, with strong legal frameworks and insurance mechanisms but persistent coordination and motivation gaps.
- Trøndelag, by contrast, demonstrates an advanced institutional architecture with explicit legal obligations and functioning data systems, yet still faces behavioural and incentive-related barriers that limit collaboration.

This gradient confirms that while capacity and opportunity can evolve over time, motivation and coordination remain the decisive factors for system-wide change.

5.1 Political and Institutional Dimensions

One of the persistent barriers across all three regions is fragmented governance and unclear institutional mandates. In Gabrovo, there is limited understanding of which authorities hold relevant data or responsibility for its use. Valencia faces issues of coordination between national and regional levels, while in Trøndelag, rules exist but are interpreted inconsistently across municipalities. These political–capability gaps reflect uncertainty about “who owns” the process of data exchange.

However, political drivers are also visible. In both Valencia and Trøndelag, the existence of legal obligations for risk assessment and reporting creates formal entry points for more systematic data use. Where mandates are clear, responsibilities explicit, and collaboration frameworks formalised, institutions begin to perceive data sharing as part of their official role rather than an optional activity. Political continuity, empowered focal institutions, and inter-agency trust therefore emerge as critical drivers.

5.2 Economic and Resource Conditions

Economic barriers are primarily linked to misaligned incentives and limited understanding of benefits. In Gabrovo, there are no financial mechanisms, market advantages, or cost-sharing arrangements that would encourage institutions or businesses to invest in data infrastructure. In Valencia, although compulsory insurance provides a potential driver, the lack of direct financial benefit or co-funded data pipelines limits motivation. Trøndelag's insurance market shows progress, with climate-adapted products offering tangible benefits, yet these remain limited in scale.

The lesson across cases is that economic opportunity must be both clear and shared. When financial savings, reduced losses, or improved budget justification are visibly tied to data collaboration, behaviour begins to shift. Cost-benefit framing, transparent use cases, and shared funding schemes are therefore among the most promising drivers in this dimension.

5.3 Sociocultural and Behavioural Factors

Across all three cases, sociocultural barriers stand out as the most pervasive and the least addressed. A low level of social awareness, weak norms of reciprocity, and limited public engagement consistently undermine the willingness of actors to share data. Gabrovo illustrates a near absence of social or reputational incentives; Valencia reports moderate climate-awareness but little recognition of the role of data; and Trøndelag, despite higher environmental consciousness, shows that collaboration still depends on individual champions rather than institutionalised norms.

The lack of trust between public and private sectors and among public agencies is a recurring theme. Actors fear data misuse, reputational harm, or political exposure, which discourages openness. These are behavioural barriers that cannot be resolved solely through regulation.

Conversely, emerging drivers include the establishment of Communities of Practice (CoPs), peer learning networks, and visible success stories that normalise sharing behaviour. Trøndelag's municipal climate-adaptation networks and Valencia's insurance data mechanisms provide early examples of how community-level engagement and recognition can shift social expectations. Building trust, transparency, and reputational value around collaboration is thus essential for systemic progress.

5.4 Technological and Infrastructural Context

Technological capacity varies widely but follows a similar pattern: tools exist, but integration and use remain inconsistent. Gabrovo and Valencia both reports fragmented systems and weak interoperability, while Trøndelag’s digital infrastructure is relatively advanced but not consistently utilised. This points to a behavioural bottleneck rather than a purely technical one: the absence of routines and confidence that turn access into actual use.

Drivers in this domain include shared technical standards, unified data protocols, federated access models, and training that embed digital tools into regular workflows. When technology is supported by clear operational guidance and user-friendly systems, it becomes a behavioural enabler rather than a passive asset.

5.5 Environmental and Motivational Dynamics

Environmental realities act as powerful awareness triggers but do not automatically translate into sustained motivation. In all three regions, increasingly frequent climate-related events have raised the visibility of risk, yet awareness remains reactive and short-lived. The gap lies in linking these experiences to concrete, ongoing actions.

Drivers emerge when environmental events are converted into feedback mechanisms, for example, when loss data after storms or floods are used to inform planning, justify investments, or adjust insurance schemes. This transformation from awareness to institutional learning is crucial for long-term motivation.

5.6 Overall Conclusions

The combined PESTEL–COM-B analysis confirms that **structural enablers alone cannot ensure effective data sharing**. Political will, regulatory frameworks, and technical systems are necessary but insufficient unless matched by behavioural conditions—capability, opportunity, and motivation—that make collaboration routine and self-reinforcing.

Key cross-cutting **barriers** identified include:

- Fragmented mandates and unclear institutional roles (Political–Capability).
- Misaligned or absent economic incentives (Economic–Opportunity).

- Weak trust and conservative social norms that discourage openness (Social–Motivation).
- Inconsistent use of available technology and lack of operational standards (Technological–Capability).
- Environmental urgency that raises awareness but not sustained engagement (Environmental–Motivation).
- Legal ambiguity and fear of breaching confidentiality (Legal–Opportunity).

Corresponding **drivers** that can enable change include:

- Clear mandates, coordination frameworks, and political continuity.
- Explicit cost–benefit communication and shared investment models.
- Peer influence and Communities of Practice that normalise data exchange.
- Federated, interoperable systems supported by training and SOPs.
- Use of environmental evidence to demonstrate real benefits of sharing.
- Transparent governance and clear legal guidance that institutionalise trust.

In sum, the matrix demonstrates that effective data sharing depends on **aligning structural readiness with behavioural enablers**. By combining the external (PESTEL) and internal (COM-B) dimensions, the analysis provides a nuanced picture of where interventions are most needed and how they can be tailored to each regional context. It highlights that progress will come not from technological fixes or new mandates alone, but from cultivating the **behavioural capability, opportunity, and motivation** required to turn cooperation into an everyday practice across Europe’s climate-risk data ecosystem.

6. References

EU Flood Directive on the assessment and management of flood risks (2007/60/EC).

[Link](#)

EU General Data Protection Regulation (95/46/EC) [Link](#)

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EC. 2023. Communication on progress on implementing reporting of preventing and managing disaster risk in Europe mentioned in article 6 of the Union Civil Protection Mechanism (Decision No 1313/2013/EU). [Link](#)

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EU Taxonomy; Regulation 2020/852/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 June 2020 on the establishment of a framework to facilitate sustainable investment, and amending Regulation (EU) 2019/2088. [Link](#)

Insurance Europe, about [Link](#)

OECD Managing-climate-risks-facing-up-to-losses-and-damages [Link](#)

ANNEX I

Example of regulation (Norwegian law) on confidentiality to financial institutions regarding sharing data (§ 9-6. *Taushetsplikt om kundeforhold mv.*

(Google translate):

The financial institution act/§ 9-6. Duty of confidentiality regarding customer relations, etc.

(1) Employees and shop stewards in a financial enterprise are obliged to prevent unauthorized persons from gaining access to or knowledge of information about customers' and others' business or personal relationships that they become aware of during the performance of their work or duties for the enterprise, unless they are required by law or regulations given by law either has a duty to provide information or is given permission to provide information that is otherwise subject to a duty of confidentiality. The same applies to anyone who carries out assignments for a financial undertaking, even if the person in question is not employed by the undertaking. When special considerations dictate it, the Norwegian Financial Supervisory Authority can completely or partially revoke the obligation of confidentiality.

(2) The duty of confidentiality pursuant to the first paragraph does not prevent information from being disclosed with the written consent of those who have a right to confidentiality.)

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